

INBESTSOIL HANDBOOK

SOIL SAMPLING
PROCEDURES AND METHODOLOGIES FOR THE
MEASUREMENT OF SOIL
HEALTH INDICATORS

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Handbook of soil sampling procedures and methodologies for the measurement of soil health indicators

This handbook is a milestone (MS05) achieved in “WP3: Economic valuation of the soil ecosystem services and the impacts of soil interventions” of the InBestSoil project, financed by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, under grant agreement N°. 101091099.

Edited by Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT)

Design by June Communications SRL

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DATE OF RELEASE: March 2024

FIRST EDITION

Preface

InBestSoil project aims to co-create a framework for investment in the conservation and recovery of soil health by developing an economic valuation system of the ecosystem services delivered by healthy soil, the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentives. This will allow public and private organizations to give economic value to their actions over soil health, co-design strategies with local stakeholders, and work collectively to deliver national and EU policy ambitions. For this purpose, InBestSoil has selected seven lighthouses and two living labs, which provide a total of nine study areas across four biogeographic regions from Europe (Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, and Mediterranean) and four different land uses (agriculture, forest, urban, mining), as models for co-creation and co-design (multi-actor approach, responsible research and innovation, and open science). Following the definitions given by the Implementation Plan for the Soil Mission, we consider a lighthouse as a place for the demonstration of long-term solutions that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement and a living lab as the collaboration between some research and innovation ecosystems, which involve regional stakeholders in systemic research and co-design, to improve the effectiveness of new practices on soil health jointly.

After the co-selection of the most appropriate indicators to determine soil health in each living lab or lighthouse under a participatory consultation, the soil will be collected in all lighthouses and living labs.

The values of the soil health indicators, representing different ecosystem services in which soil is involved, will be the base for the economic valuation of these ecosystem services, using market and non-market valuation methods.

Thus, it is necessary to define a series of standardised methodologies that allow for the attainment of comparable results for all selected soil health indicators. This handbook covers all the methods used for this purpose in the InBestSoil project, specifically in Work Package 3. Each chapter of the handbook includes a first section with a slight explanation of the indicator to be measured, followed by a list with the necessary materials, a step-by-step explanation of the procedure, the calculations required, and a series of essential tips or points to improve the process. This handbook is divided into eight sections:

- The first one is focused on the procedures agreed upon for soil sampling.
- The second section focuses on crop yield, plant biomass, richness, biodiversity and richness.
- The third section assesses soil biodiversity and focuses on soil bacteria, fungi and protists.
- The fourth section considers the methods to characterise soil fertility and the pollutants present in the soil.
- The fifth section includes methods related to the soil structure, water availability and carbon sequestration. The sixth section is dedicated to the characterisation of soil greenhouse emissions. The seventh section is related to satellite-based indicators for characterising vegetation cover, erosion features and crop status. The last section is dedicated to cultural indicators.
- Numerous people from various countries have participated in realising this handbook, and the editors want to express their special thanks to all of them.

CONTENT

1 SOIL SAMPLING GENERAL INTRODUCTION	6
1.1. SOIL SAMPLING FOR BULK DENSITY	7
1.2. SOIL SAMPLING FOR PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES	10
2. CROP YIELD, PLANT BIOMASS, PLANT RICHNESS, BIODIVERSITY AND DENSITY	16
2.1. PLANT BIOMASS, PLANT RICHNESS, BIODIVERSITY AND DENSITY	17
2.2. CROP YIELD/WOOD PRODUCTION	21
3. ASSESSMENT OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY	25
3.1. MICROBIAL BIOMASS (PLFAS)	26
3.2. MICROBIAL FUNCTIONAL DIVERSITY: ESTIMATION OF ABUNDANCE OF SELECTED MICROBIAL GENE SEQUENCES BY QUANTITATIVE PCR FROM DNA DIRECTLY EXTRACTED FROM SOIL (C AND N CYCLES)	40
3.3. SOIL DNA EXTRACTION AND PURIFICATION	61
3.4. BACTERIAL AND ARCHAEAL GENETIC DIVERSITY: SSR RNA GENE AMPLICON SEQUENCING	71
3.5. FUNGAL/MYCORRHIZA GENETIC DIVERSITY: FUNGAL ITS ILLUMINA AMPLICON SEQUENCING	75
3.6. PROTISTS GENETIC DIVERSITY AND RELATIVE ABUNDANCE: 18S RRNA GENE AMPLICON SEQUENCING	85
3.7. EXCREMENT BAITS AS A PROXY FOR COPROPHAGOUS FAUNA ACTIVITY	90
3.8. PITFALL TRAPS FOR SOIL EPIGEAN FAUNA	95
3.9. QBS INDEX	99
4. SOIL FERTILITY AND POLLUTION ASSESSMENT	104
4.1. SOIL PH	105
4.2. ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY	111
4.3. TOTAL NITROGEN	116
4.4. INORGANIC NITROGEN (NITRATES AND AMMONIUM)	120
4.5. AVAILABLE P IN THE SOIL (BRAY / OLSEN)	127
4.6. OXALATE EXTRACTABLE AI AND FE	136
4.7. AVAILABLE METALS AND METALLOIDS (AS, CD, MO, CO, CU, CR, MN, ZN, HG, NI, PB, SB AND V)	145
4.8. AVAILABLE METALS AND METALLOIDS (AS, CD, MO, CO, CU, CR, MN, ZN, HG, NI, PB, SB AND V)	149
4.9. TOTAL METALS AND METALLOIDS (AS, CD, CO, CR, CU, HG, NI, PB, SB, V AND ZN)	155
4.10 AVAILABLE B	161
4.11 AVAILABLE S (SULFATE)	165
4.12 TOTAL PESTICIDES	169
5. SOIL STRUCTURE, WATER AVAILABILITY AND SOIL CARBON SEQUESTRATION	185
5.1. BULK DENSITY	186
5.2. COARSE FRAGMENTS DETERMINATION	190
5.3. PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION AND TEXTURE	193
5.4. AGGREGATE STABILITY AND SIZE DISTRIBUTION	198
5.5. WATER CONTENT AT FIELD CAPACITY	203
5.6. SOIL MOISTURE	207
5.7. SOIL POROSITY	211
5.8. ORGANIC MATTER AND CARBON CONTENT	214
5.9. PARTICULATE ORGANIC CARBON AND MINERAL-ASSOCIATED ORGANIC CARBON FRACTIONS	221
6. GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS	227
6.1. GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS	228
7. SATELLITE-BASED INDICATORS	233
7.1. ALBEDO	234
7.2. LAND SURFACE TEMPERATURE	238
7.3. GROSS PRIMARY PRODUCTIVITY (GPP)	242
7.4. SOIL SEALING	246
7.5. DROUGHT STRESS INDEX	252
7.6. MOISTURE STRESS INDEX	256
7.7. NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE WATER INDEX	259
7.8. NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE MOISTURE INDEX	263
7.9. EROSION FEATURES	267
7.10. BARE SOIL INDEX	272
7.11. NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE VEGETATION INDEX	278
7.12. NET PRIMARY PRODUCTIVITY	284
7.13. PLANT SENESCING REFLECTANCE INDEX (PSRI)	288
7.14. FOREST COVER	293
7.15. VEGETATION COVER	299
7.16. PLANT PHENOLOGY INDEX (PPI)	303
7.17. DRY MATTER PRODUCTIVITY	307
7.18. LEAF AREA INDEX	309
7.19. PRESENCE OF GREEN NATURAL ELEMENTS	313
8. CULTURAL INDICATORS	318
8.1 CULTURAL ECOSYSTEM SERVICES	319

01 SOIL SAMPLING GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Soil sampling for bulk density

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Principle & Application

Soil bulk density refers to the weight (mass) of soil per unit of volume and is generally expressed in g per cm³. The weight of a soil sample can be easily determined, while collecting a specific volume of soil is less obvious.

Thus, to accurately measure the soil bulk density of an agricultural field, soil samples should be taken with care. The sampling procedure selected here is the one using cylindrical cores. The cylinder is pressed or hammered into the soil. The cylinder is removed gently, thereby extracting a sample of known volume.

Using a cylindrical core enables the sampler to take a known soil volume. Previous studies have demonstrated that the type of cylindrical cores does not significantly influence the bulk density measurements. The critical factor is that the sampler must remove the core used in such a way that the core remains filled with soil.

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EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Bulk-density cylinders (metal rings) with known volume, preferably with removable lids at both ends
- Sampling bags, preferably with a twist tie
- Permanent marker
- Spatula and shovel
- Hammer
- Piece of flat wooden plank
- Retractable tape measure
- Core sampler

PROCEDURE

Prepare a flat surface at the first selected sampling spot by scraping away the loose upper layer with a shovel or spatula.

Press the ring entirely into the soil manually or with a hammer and the wooden plank, preferably till 1 cm below the prepared surface. You can use a second ring and the wooden plank to hammer the cylinder deeper into the soil.

Remove the ring with the help of a spatula or shovel. Be sure to avoid soil falling from the ring.

Remove excessive soil with a knife until the upper and lower surface of the soil in the cylinder is flat.

Close both sides of the ring if you transport the soil within the ring. If you will use the same ring for several samples or do not have the lids to close the rings, transfer the soil of a ring to a plastic bag and code it appropriately. Close the bag with a twist tie.

Repeat the procedure (Steps 1-5) on an additional four spots well spread over the selected field.

In the lab: store the soil samples at room temperature.

REMARKS

The method is not intended for loose, sandy soils. Additionally, dry or hard soils can shatter when the cylinder is hammered into the soil. In this case, pressing the cylinder into the soil reduces the risk of shattering the sample.

The cylindrical cores should have a thin, sharp edge to avoid compaction during sampling. If compression is excessive, the soil core may not be a valid sample for analysis. Rock fragments can damage the cores and interfere with the sampling.

1.2 Soil sampling for physicochemical and microbiological properties

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Principle & Application

A composite soil sample is taken to assess a number of soil physicochemical and microbiological diversity. A composite sample is taken by an auger in different locations that represent the area characterized by the LUCAS point (Figure X). First of all, the soil sample is taken at the LUCAS point (central point), and after that, 4 additional soil samples are taken at each site, a two-meter distance from the central point in the shape of a cross (along the cardinal compass point). The five samples are mixed to create a composite sample. Soil depth is 0 to 30 cm, and the soil composite sample should be at least 1 or 1.5 kg.

Upon arrival in the lab, after sampling, the soil samples have to be homogenized manually and divided into different parts (Figure 1) :

- Part 1: 500 g sieved < 2 mm for physicochemical properties in a plastic bag.
- Part 2: 500 g not sieved for aggregate stability in a rigid container.
- Part 3: 50 g undisturbed soil for biological properties and mineral nitrogen (for mineral N analysis, sieved soil (< 2 mm) is needed) in a plastic bag. For this part, use a spoon or spatula cleaned with 70% ethanol.

SOIL COMPOSITE SAMPLES

LUCAS point: soil composites samples for analyses

Figure 1: Soil composite samples according to LUCAS point

Soil samples for physicochemical analyses are stored at room temperature (parts 1 and 2), while soil samples for biological analyses are stored at -20°C or -80°C for extended storage (part 3). In addition, keep an aliquot of each soil sample in case you need to send more samples and determine coarse fragments in your soil samples. All soil samples will be sent to UPCT (Virginia Sánchez-Navarro) for physicochemical and microbiological analyses. Soil samples for physicochemical analyses will be sent at room temperature. However, soil samples for microbiological analyses will be sent in a polystyrene box with ice plates and express delivery (max. 24 h time).

SOIL SAMPLING AND SHIPMENT PROCESS

Soil sampling and shipment process: Physical, chemical and microbiological samples

In the lab

For biological analyses and mineral N:

30-50 g

Storage: -20°C (-80°C for long storage)
Send to UPCT with **ice plates, polystyrene box and express delivery (max. 24 h time)** for DNA extraction and mineral N

IMPORTANT
Keep an aliquot of each soil sample, in case you need to send us more samples

Polystyrene box

For physicochemical analyses:

Dry soil at room temperature for 7-10 days

± 1 kg

IMPORTANT
Keep an aliquot of each soil sample, in case you need to send us more samples

500 g sieved (<2mm)

Storage: room temperature
Send to UPCT (for PQ analysis, PLFAs, IR spectroscopy, etc)

500 g not sieved (rigid container)

Storage: room temperature
Send to UPCT for aggregates

Figure 2: Soil sampling and shipment process

Dried samples for physicochemical analyses are stored at room temperature as the lack of water ensures preservation. The soil samples for microbiological analyses are stored at 4°C until shipment to minimize changes in the analyzed soil biological properties. Upon arrival in the receiving laboratory, samples for microbial diversity assessment may be stored frozen at -20 °C for several weeks or at -80 °C for several months before analysis. A list with sample codes is added in the transport box.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- AUGER
- SAMPLING BAGS
PREFERABLY WITH A TWIST TIE
- PERMANENT MARKER
- SPATULA AND SHOVEL
- MEASURING DEVICE
- BOX
- SPRAY BOTTLE WITH 70% ETHANOL
- ROLL OF PAPER
- COOL BOX WITH ICE PLATES
(WHEN THE TEMPERATURE IS ABOVE 15°C)
- GLOVES

PROCEDURE

Before going to the field, please label strong plastic sampling bags appropriately.

Wear gloves.

Take a composite soil sample at the LUCAS point (central point) with a depth between 0 and 30 cm, and after that, four additional soil samples will be taken at each site, two-meter distance from the central point in the shape of a cross (along cardinal compass point). The five samples are mixed to create a composite sample.

At each sampling point, press the auger vertically in the soil. Use both hands if needed.

Twist the auger half turn up to sampling depth (between 0 and 30 cm) and pull it out at a slight angle in an attempt to keep the soil core positioned into the auger.

Move the auger into the already labelled plastic bag and use the spatula to release the soil from the auger into the plastic bag.

Go to the next sampling point and repeat this procedure until all sampling points are sampled.

Close the sample bag with a twist tie, mix the soil and separate an aliquot (50 g) in a cool box with cool packs for microbiological analyses and mineral N. Place the rest of the soil sample for physicochemical analyses in a box.

Before going to the next field, the sampling material (auger) is disinfected with 70% ethanol and wiped dry with paper. This should mainly prevent the carry-over of soil-containing organisms from one sample to the other.

REMARKS

Taking soil samples that are very wet or dry should be avoided. If conditions are unfavourable, it is recommended to postpone the sampling by a few days.

It is recommended not to use sampling bags with a zip lock. The zip lock is not strong enough to keep the bag closed at all times. It can easily cause spilling of soil into the cool box or even cause carry-over of soil from one sampling bag into the other.

02

CROP YIELD, PLANT BIOMASS,
PLANT RICHNESS, BIODIVERSITY
AND DENSITY

2.1 Plant biomass, plant richness, biodiversity and density

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Principle & Application

The crop growth of arable crops can be controlled with measurement of the above-ground biomass. Although above-ground biomass can be measured in different moments of the crop, measuring this parameter at flowering provides an excellent indicator of crop growth at a critical crop development stage.

The above-ground biomass measurement consists of the collection of the total above-ground crop biomass within a known surface. Once in the laboratory, this fresh biomass is dried out in an oven and weighed.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- 0.5 M RULER
- SCISSORS
- LABELLED PAPER OR PLASTIC BAGS
- ALUMINIUM TRAYS
- OVEN
- BALANCE
- DATA RECORDING SHEET/NOTEBOOK
- RECORDING MATERIAL (PEN, PENCIL, ETC.)

Reagents

No reagents

PROCEDURE

Place quadrants (0.5×0.5) within each plot, located at the center and corners along a diagonal line within the plot. Five replicates per plot are recommended to account for spatial variability in the field.

Vegetation will be sampled in each quadrat, and all vascular plant species and their cover and density will be recorded. Species richness will be defined as the sum of distinct species in the five quadrats per plot.

Clip all the plants in each quadrant within the plot to ground level and place them in a paper or plastic bag.

Dry at 65°C for 48 h.

Weigh the biomass.

Calculations

$$\text{Plant density} = \frac{\text{Number of plants}}{\text{m}^2}$$

$$\text{Species richness} = \frac{\text{Plant species}}{\text{m}^2}$$

$$\text{Plant biomass} \left(\frac{\text{DM}}{\text{m}^2} \right) = \frac{\text{Dry biomass weight (g)}}{\text{Quadrant (m}^2\text{)}}$$

REFERENCES

- Liu et al., 2022. Overgrazing, not haying, decreases grassland topsoil organic carbon by decreasing plant species richness along an aridity gradient in Northern China. *Agr Ecosyst Environ*, 332, 107935.

2.2. Crop yield. Wood production

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Principle & Application

Crop yield is known as the quantity of agricultural production harvested per unit of land area. Crop yield is the metric most widely used to assess the productivity of a farm and the related economic benefits, and it is usually expressed as kilograms (or metric tons) per hectare. In addition, crop yield can be also referred as the quantity of useful parts or economic product of a crop harvested at an appropriate development stage on a unit of land area (Fischer 2015).

To estimate crop yield, the amount of the harvested product (grain, tuber, etc.) for a given crop is weighed in a sample area (Álvaro-Fuentes et al. 2019).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- HARVESTER FOR CROP YIELD OR SAW FOR WOOD PRODUCTION
- BALANCE.
- BAGS/BASKETS.
- DATA RECORDING SHEET/NOTEBOOK.
- RECORDING MATERIAL (PEN, PENCIL, ETC.)

PROCEDURE

Crop yield can be measured by harvesting completely each experimental plot using either a commercial combine harvester or manually if it is the case for the particular crop, depending on the cultural practice of the region. Wood production can be measured by cutting down each experimental plot completely using a saw.

Harvest all the commercial product in the harvesting area, place it in a bag/basket, and, finally, weigh the product collected.

Calculations

To determine the crop yield, the following expression is applied:

$$\text{Crop Yield (kg/ha)} = \frac{\text{Total weight of the commercial product (kg)}}{\text{Harvested area (ha)}}$$

Remarks

In multiple cropping or intercropping systems, the yield of each crop obtained within a given year and piece of land must be summed to obtain an annual land production value.

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- Fischer, R. A. (2015). Definitions and Determination of Crop Yield, Yield Gaps, and of Rates of Change. Field Crops Res 182, 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2014.12.006>

**03 ASSESSMENT OF SOIL
BIODIVERSITY**

3.1 Microbial biomass (PLFAs)

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Principle & Application

The phospholipids are formed by fatty acids, glycerol or sphingosine (depending on the type of phospholipids) and a phosphate group. Since 1980, phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA) have been frequently used as biomarkers and to determine the microbial biomass (total biomass and biomass of specific groups of microorganisms) due to the fact that while some fatty acids are unspecific (Table 4.1), others are characteristic of determined microorganisms (White and Findlay 1988).

The carbon chains can be saturated (carbons appear linked by simple bonds) or unsaturated (when double bonds appear between carbons) (Benatar et al. 2011). Carbon α is the one that belongs to the carboxyl group, while the furthest is carbon ω . However, when numbering them the 1 is the furthest from the carboxyl group (the ω carbon). When naming them, the nomenclature usually used is "total carbon atoms number of the fatty acid:number of double bonds ω position of double bonds from the methyl end of the molecule separated by commas". To indicate a cis or trans configuration, the letter "c" or "t" is usually added.

Group	Biomarker (Fatty Acid)
Bacteria	Gram-positive (G+) + Gram-negative (G-)
G+	Firmicutes + Actinobacteria
Firmicutes	i14:0, i15:0, i16:0, i17:0, i18, α 15:0, α 17:0, α 18:0, α 19:0
Actinobacteria	10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, 10Me18:0
G-	cy17:0, cy19:0, 16:1 ω 7, 16:1 ω 9, 17:1 ω 8, 18:1 ω 7
Fungi	AMF + Zygomycota + Ascomycota and Basidiomycota + unspecific fungal
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF)	16:1 ω 5c
Zygomycota	18:1 ω 9c
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	18:2 ω 6c
Unspecific fungal PLFA	18:3 ω 6,9,12
Unspecific microbial PLFA	14:0, 15:0, 16:0, 17:0, 18:0, 20:0, 20:4 ω 6,9,12,15
Total microbial PLFA	bacterial + fungal + unspecific microbial

Table 4. Fatty acid biomarkers (Joergesen, 2022)

The prefixes "i" or "a" indicated iso- or anteiso-branching; "br" indicates an unknown branching configuration type (Bååth 2003; Kaur et al. 2005). If there is a methyl group in carbon 10, "10Me" is added, and "cy" is added if there is a cyclopropyl group (Frostegård et al. 1993).

The PLFA analysis of soil microbial community can be divided into four parts: extraction of lipids from the soil, fractionation of the different types of lipids (neutral lipids, glycolipids and polar lipids), mid-alkaline methanolysis of the different lipids to convert their components, the fatty acids, into volatile methyl esters, and analysis of these by gas chromatography (Frostegård et al. 1993, Díaz-Raviña et al. 2006).

Procedure

Preparation of reagents

- 5 N NaOH solution. Weight 200 g of NaOH in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 mL with deionized water.
- 0.15 M citrate buffer, pH 4: dilute 28.82 g of citric acid in 850 mL of water and add the 5N NaOH solution to adjust the pH to 4 before diluting to 1000 mL with deionized water. This solution must be prepared at the time of use.
- Bligh and Dyer (B&D) reagent: mixt CHCl₃:MeOH: citrate buffer in a proportion 1:2:0.8 (v/v/v).
- MeOH:toluene: Mix both solutions in a proportion 1:1 (v/v).
- Hexane: CHCl₃ Mix both solutions in a proportion 4:1 (v/v).
- Acetic acid 1M. Add 57.2 mL of acetic acid in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 mL with deionized water.
- KOH 0.2 M in MeOH. Weight 11.22 g of KOH in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 mL with MeOH. This solution must be prepared at the time of use.
- Standard methyl nonadecanoate (Std 19:0, molecular weight 312.54 g). Dissolve 115 µg of the standard in 5 mL of hexane (concentration 23 µg·mL⁻¹). This solution must be prepared daily.
- Detergent free of phosphates (2% in deionized water type II).

Procedure

1. Lipid extraction

- Weigh between 0.5 and 6 grams of dry soil (0.5 – 1.5 g if high OM -Organic Matter- content; 3 – 6 g if low OM content) and place in 50 mL Teflon tubes. Moist, air-dried, frozen or freeze-dried soil samples can be used. Blanks without soil, treated under the same conditions, are prepared in each batch of samples.
- Add 10 mL of B&D reagent, shake with vortex for 1 min and keep 2 hours at room temperature to allow the compounds to be extracted.
- Centrifuge for 11 minutes at 1677 x g and transfer the supernatant to a 50 mL Teflon or glass tube.
- To complete the extraction, repeat the process, adding B&D to the residue. Add the supernatants to the 50 mL tube mixing both supernatants.

- Add 4 mL of chloroform and 4 mL of citrate buffer to the extract obtained and to shake in the vortex for 1 min.
- The suspension is left overnight to extract the lipids in the organic phase. Another option is to centrifuge for 11 min at 1677 x g.
- The lower phase (organic) is extracted with a Pasteur pipette. An aliquot of 3 mL (high OM content soil) or 5 mL (low OM content soil) of this phase is evaporate to dryness at 40 °C under a stream of nitrogen in a dry block heater. The rest of the extract is stored at 4 °C until the end of the procedure.
- Dry samples are frozen at -20 °C. In case of continuing with the fractionation on the same day, it is not necessary to freeze.

Procedure

2. Fractionation

The second step consists of separating the different lipid fractions.

Dried samples (and thawed) are re-suspended using 100 μL of chloroform and agitation in the Vortex. This suspension is added to a silica column (SPE-SI) previously placed on 25 mL glass tubes. Repeat this process twice by adding 100 μL of CHCl_3 .

Once the lipids have been retained in the silica column, reagents of increasing polarity are applied successively to eluate the different fractions collected in different glass tubes:

- 1.5 mL of CHCl_3 to elute the neutral lipids.
- 6 mL of acetone in two 3 mL steps to separate the glycolipids.
- 1.5 mL of MeOH to eluate the polar lipids.

At the end of the fractionation, the contents of the tubes are evaporated to dryness at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under a stream of nitrogen in a dry block heater.

This method will analyse the last (polar lipids) fractions.

Procedure

3. Mild alkaline methanolysis (Transesterification)

The third step involves a transesterification reaction to convert the fatty acids of the phospholipids (PLFA) into volatile derivatives that can be measured by gas chromatography.

- Add 100 μL of the Std19:0 (23 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ concentration) to all samples.
- Evaporate hexane under a flow of nitrogen.
- Add 1 mL of the MeOH: toluene (1: 1) mixture and shake in a vortex for 5 s.
- Add 1 mL of 0.2 M KOH in MeOH, shake in a vortex for 5 seconds and incubate in a bath (at 37 °C) for 15 min. Let the samples cool for some minutes at room temperature.
- Add 2 ml of hexane: CHCl_3 (4: 1), 0.3 mL of 1 M acetic acid and 2 ml of deionized water.
- Stir for 1 min in a vortex, check that the pH of the lower phase is around 6, centrifuge 11 min at 1677 x g, and remove the upper phase to a glass container with a Pasteur pipette. This step must be repeated by adding 2 mL of hexane: CHCl_3 , stirring and centrifuging again.
- Evaporate to dryness the solvents in the samples under a stream of nitrogen without heating. It is essential to remove the samples when the last drop of the solvent evaporates to avoid losses of the more volatile fatty acids. Freeze the dry samples at -20 °C until it will be analyzed.

Procedure

4. GC Analysis

The last step is the sample analysis on a gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID). A HP5 (phenylmethyl silicone) capillary column (50 m longitude, 0.2 mm internal diameter, 0.33 μm film thickness) is used.

Chromatographic conditions (Frostegård et al. 1993):

- Carrier gas was He (flow 0.8 mL·min⁻¹)
- Detector temperature: 230 °C
- Injector temperature: 230 °C, injection was made in splitless mode
- Oven temperature program: Initial temperature 80 °C for 1 min, increasing first at 20 °C·min⁻¹ to 160 °C and then at 5 °C·min⁻¹ to reach 270 °C, remaining at this temperature for 5 min.

The frozen sample is thawed to room temperature.

Add 100 μL of hexane to dissolve the sample and transfer it to GC vials.

1 μL of this solution is analysed by GC-FID by duplicated.

The PLFAs, identified by the relative retention times compared with those obtained for the standards and the peak areas are quantified by adding, before the transesterification step, methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0) as internal standard.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- pH-meter
- Vortex or Multivortex agitator
- Centrifuge
- Sample concentrator in N₂ atmosphere
- 50 mL Teflon centrifuge tubes with a screw cap
- Glass tubes with a screw cap
- Erlenmeyer flasks
- Beakers
- Volumetric flasks
- Graduated cylinder
- Pasteur pipettes
- Micro-centrifugation tubes of 1.5 or 2 mL
- Petri dishes
- GC vials
- Spatulas and tweezers
- Racks
- LCR Cartridges Bond Elut SI (SPE) normal phase (polar)

Reagents

- Citric acid (C₆H₈O₇)
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Potassium hydroxide (KOH)
- Acetone (C₃H₆O)
- Acetic acid (CH₃COOH)
- Chloroform (CHCl₃)
- Hexane (C₆H₁₄)
- Methanol (CH₃OH)
- Toluene (C₇H₈)
- Methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0, C₂₀H₄₀O₂)
- Water deionized type I (Resistivity 18 MΩ-cm, TOC <5 ppb) used to prepare the reagents and water deionized type II (Resistivity >5 MΩ-cm) to wash the material
- Phosphate-free detergent

REMARKS

Due to the high sensitivity of the method, impurities from the reagents and ineffective cleaning of the material used can cause serious contamination problems that can be detected in the blanks (without soil).

It is important to wash the material with a phosphate-free detergent. All clean and dry glass material (non-volumetric) must also undergo a heat treatment at 400 °C for at least 6 hours to eliminate any other organic matter, including lipid contaminants.

All reagents used are of analytical grade, except n-hexane, which is the solvent for GC chromatography.

During the process, the following security measures must be taken into account:

1. Work in the gas extraction cabinet and, if it is not possible, use a mask with a filter for organic solvents,
2. Wear a dust mask to weigh the powder reagents.
3. Use gloves and safety glasses whenever there is any possibility of splashes.

CALCULATIONS

Each identified PLFA is quantified (nmol·g⁻¹ of dry soil) in each sample using the following equation:

$$\text{PLFA (nmol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Area PLFA sample}}{\text{Area 19:0 sample}} \times \text{CIStd19:0 added} \times \text{CF} \times \text{V} \times \frac{1}{\text{Dry soil weight}}$$

Where:

- Area PLFA sample is the peak area of each PLFA identified in the sample
- Area 19:0 is the peak area of the internal standard methylnonadecanoate (IStd19:0) in the same sample
- CIStd19:0 is the amount of internal standard, and IStd19:0 is added in step 3 to each sample, expressed in nmol.

$$\text{CIStd19:0 added (nmol)} = \frac{23000 \text{ ng} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} \times 10^{-1} \text{ mL}}{312.54 \text{ ng} \cdot \text{nmol}^{-1}}$$

CF is the correction factor determined by the recovery of the internal standard to each sample, calculated as:

$$\text{CF} = \frac{\text{Area 19:0 blank}}{\text{Area 19:0 sample}}$$

Where:

- Area 19:0 blank is the peak area of IStd19:0 in the blank.
- Area 19:0 sample is the peak area of IStd19:0 in the sample.

V is the factor obtained from the quotient between the total volume of CHCl₃ used in the lipids. extraction, 7.95 mL, and the aliquot volume used for fractionation (3 or 5 mL) (step 1).

Total PLFA microbial biomass estimations

The sum of the content of all the PLFAs (around a total of 30 – 35 unspecific and specific to different microbial groups) identified and quantified in each sample was used to obtain the total PLFA biomass (nmol·g⁻¹ of dry soil).

Microbial PLFA biomass of specific microbial groups

The content of each PLFAs biomarkers characteristic of the specific microbial groups is summed to obtain the PLFA biomass of these groups (see Table 4.1).

It should be noticed that the criteria of the PLFAs characteristics of specific microbial groups could differ among authors (Frostegård et al. 1993; Frostegård and Bååth 1996; Zelles 1999; Kaur et al. 2005; Díaz-Raviña et al. 2006); thus in these biomass estimations, the reference used should be included.

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3.2 Microbial functional diversity: Estimation of abundance of selected microbial gene sequences by quantitative PCR from DNA directly extracted from soil (C and N cycles)

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Principle & Application

Carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles are driven mainly by microbial activities (Burgin et al. 2011). In this protocol, microbial C and N cycling gene abundance is determined by qPCR targeting the genes *ureC*, *amoA*, *narG*, *nirK*, and *nifH* involved in the N cycle and the genes *cbbL* and *GH7* involved in the C cycle.

Ammonification is the process of mineralizing organic N to ammonium (NH_4^+). It is the first step in organic N decomposition and is often called N mineralization (Hopkinson and Giblin 2008). Ammonium can then be assimilated and incorporated into amino acids or used for other metabolic purposes (Strock 2008).

PRINCIPLE & APPLICATION

Urease is a nickel-containing enzyme that catalyzes the conversion of urea to ammonia and carbonic acid (Reed 2001). The ureC gene is the largest of the genes encoding urease functional subunits and contains several highly conserved regions (Su et al. 2013).

Nitrification is the biological oxidation of ammonia (NH_3) or ammonium (NH_4^+) to oxidized N in the form of nitrite (NO_2^-) and further to nitrate (NO_3^-). Nitrification is of pivotal importance in agricultural systems since it increases the mobility of N through the soil matrix, strongly influencing N retention in the system (Norton and Ouyang 2019). Ammonia oxidation is considered to be the rate-limiting step of nitrification. It is catalyzed by the ammonia monooxygenase enzyme (AMO), encoded by the amoA gene (Li et al. 2015).

Denitrification is the reduction of nitrate (NO_3^-) to nitrous oxide or dinitrogen and is the primary biological mechanism by which fixed nitrogen returns to the atmosphere from soil and water. This removal of soluble nitrogen oxide (N_2O) from the biosphere is essential in agriculture, where it can account for significant soil nitrogen fertiliser losses (Henry et al. 2004). A phylogenetically broad group of bacteria can reduce nitrate (NO_3^-) into nitrite (NO_2^-), which can then be reduced into gaseous nitrogen compounds by denitrification or into NH_4^+ by dissimilatory nitrate reduction in ammonium (DNRA). Denitrification is the dominant process in soils and lake sediment.

PRINCIPLE & APPLICATION

The ability of facultative anaerobic bacteria to respire nitrate when oxygen is limiting has been ascribed mainly to the activity of a membrane-bound nitrate reductase encoded by the *narGHJ* operon (Philippot and Højberg 1999). For nitrite reduction, two different types of nitrite reductase have been characterized: copper nitrite reductase encoded by the *nirK* gene and cytochrome *cd1*-nitrite reductase encoded by the *nirS* gene (Zumft 1997).

Nitrogen-fixing microorganisms are globally significant because they provide the biosphere's only natural biological source of fixed nitrogen. These organisms enzymatically transform dinitrogen gas from the atmosphere (N_2) into ammonium (NH_4^+) equivalents needed for the biosynthesis of essential cellular macromolecules. The *nifH* gene, encoding the nitrogenase reductase subunit, is the most widely sequenced marker gene used to identify nitrogen-fixing bacteria and archaea (Gaby and Buckley 2012).

Carbon fixation is inorganic C (CO_2) assimilation into organic compounds by living organisms. The Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle is the primary pathway for CO_2 fixation (Shively et al. 1986), and the most abundant protein on Earth, ribulose-1,5-biphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (RubisCO), catalyzes the first, rate-limiting step in the Calvin cycle (Ellis 1979).

PRINCIPLE & APPLICATION

The large subunit of form I RubisCO is encoded by the *cbbL* gene in bacteria (Kusian and Bowien 2006). I RubisCO proteins can be subdivided into two major groups, the green-like and red-like groups (Watson and Tabita 2006). This protocol uses the *cbbL* red-like genes to quantify carbon-fixing microorganisms.

Carbon degradation, as plant litter decomposition, is a significant source of organic carbon in soils and a critical step in nutrient recycling (Berg et al. 2001). Fungi are considered key players in organic matter decomposition in soil because of their ability to produce a wide range of extracellular enzymes, which allows them to efficiently attack the recalcitrant lignocellulose matrix that other organisms are unable to decompose (Kjøller, Struwe, and Kjøller 1982; De Boer et al. 2005).

Cellulose is the main structural component of higher plant cell walls, representing 35–50 % of plant dry weight. Through decomposition and transformation, it makes up much of soil organic matter (Lynd, Wyman, and Gerngross 1999). The Glycoside hydrolase encoding the GH7 gene is widely used to evaluate cellulose degradation (Merlin et al. 2014; Hu et al. 2019; Tian et al. 2017).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

1. PCR hood
2. PCR thermocycler
3. Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen™)
4. Horizontal electrophoresis system
5. Gel imaging system
6. Water bath
7. Shaking incubator
8. Autoclave
9. Oven
10. Real-time PCR thermocycler
11. Filtered tips
12. Pipettes
13. Low DNA binding eppendorfs
14. PCR tubes
15. Syringe filters
16. qPCR tubes
17. Cold well-loading block

REAGENTS

1. Soil DNA is extracted according to the method described in chapter 4.3.1 of this Handbook.
2. Ice
3. 70% Ethanol
4. PCR Buffer
5. BSA
6. Primers
7. TE buffer × 10: pH 8.0, 100 mL of 1 mol/L Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 20 mL of 50 mmol/L EDTA pH 8.0 in 880 mL of molecular grade water.
8. TE buffer × 1: 100 mL of TE buffer × 10 in 900 mL of H₂O.
9. Molecular-biology-grade water
10. Agarose
11. SYBR Safe DNA stain
12. DNA ladder with known lengths and concentrations of fragments.
13. NucleoMag® NGS Bead Suspension
14. pGEM®-T Easy Vector Systems with competent cells (Promega)
15. LB plates with ampicillin/IPTG/X-Gal
16. LB Broth
17. Glycerol
18. Ampicillin sodium, C₁₆H₁₈N₃NaO₄S (CAS No. 69-52-3)
19. Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Invitrogen™)
20. ISOLATE II Plasmid Mini Kit (Bioline)
21. SYBR Green® qPCR kit

1. qPCR standard preparation

qPCR standards targeting a sequence of the microbial gene of interest (GOI) are obtained from DNA extracted from soil samples according to chapter 4.3.1 of this Handbook. To select the appropriate amplicon to settle down each qPCR assay, primer pairs listed in Table 4.3.4.1 will be used for each GOI. First, using the DNA mentioned above as the template, PCR reactions will be conducted with the primer sets from Table 4.3.4.1, the reaction mixture described in Table 4.3.4.2. and the corresponding PCR cycling conditions described in Tables 4.3.4.3 to 4.3.4.9.

Function	Target gene	Gene definition	Primer name	Primer sequence (5' - 3') (*)	Annealing temperature (°C)	Amplicon size (bp)	Reference
Ammonification	ureC	urease	ureC-F ureC-R	TGGGCCTTAAAATHCAY GARGAYTGGG GGTGGTGGCACACCATN ANCAATRTC	55	340	Reed et al. (2001)
Nitrification	amoA	ammonia monoxygenase	amoA1F amoA1R	GGGGTTTCTACTGGTGG T CCCCTCKGSAAGCCTT CTTC	57	491	Rotthauwe et al. (1997)
Denitrification	narG	nitrate reductase	narG196Om 2F narG250m 2R	TAYGTSGGGCAGGAAA ACTG CGTAGAAGAAGCTGGTG CTGTT	56	110	López- Gutiérrez et al. (2004)
Denitrification	nirK	nitrite reductase	nirK876F nirK1040R	ATYGGCGGVCA YGGCGA GCCTCGATCAGRTRRTG GTT	58	165	Henry et al. (2004)
N2 fixation	nifH	nitrogenase reductase	PolF PolR	TGCGAYCCSAARGCBGA CTC ATSGCCATCATYTCRCCG GA	55	342	Poly and Bailly (2001)
Carbon fixation	cbbL	cbbL red-like gene	cbbL-RedF cbbL-RedR	AAGGAYGACGAGAACAT C TCGGTCGGSGTG TAGTT GAA	57		Selesi et al. (2005)
Carbon degradation	GH7 (fungal)	cellulose degradation	GH7-F GH7-R	GAGATCAAGCGCYCTA YGTBCA GTCRAGCCASAGCATGT TGG	56	242	Tian et al. (2017)
Cloning site			SP6 T7	ATTTAGGTGACACTATAG TAATACGACTCACTATA GGG	55		

Table 5: Primer pair for each gene of interest

1. qPCR standard preparation

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (μL)	Final Conc.
PCR buffer dNTPs mix BSA Reverse Primer Forward Primer Hot Start Extaq DNA template Sterile H2O	10x 2.5 mM/dNTP 20 mg/mL 10 μM 10 μM 5U/μl 2 ng/μl ***	2.5 μL 2 μL 0.7 μL 1 μL 1 μL 0.125 2 μL 15.675 μL	1x 200 μM/dNTP 0.56 mg/mL 400 nM 400 nM 0.025U 4 ng ***
Total volume		25 μL	

Table 4.3.4.2. Standard DNA template PCR reaction mixture

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 55°C 72°C	30 sec 30 sec 30 sec
Extension		72°C	10 min

Table 4.3.4.3. ureC PCR cycling conditions

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 57°C 72°C	25 sec 25 sec 40 sec
Extension		72°C	10 min

Table 4.3.4.4. amoA PCR cycling conditions.

1. qPCR standard preparation

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time	
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min	
Denaturation Annealing Extension Reading	6	95°C 65°C to 60°C 72°C 80°C	15 sec 30 sec 30 sec 15 sec	Touchdown (annealing temperature progressively decreased by 1°C by cycle)
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 60°C 72°C	15 sec 30 sec 30 sec	
Extension		72°C	10 min	Extension

Table 4.3.4.5. narG PCR cycling conditions

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time	
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min	
Denaturation Annealing Extension Reading	6	95°C 63°C to 58°C 72°C 80°C	15 sec 30 sec 30 sec 15 sec	Touchdown (annealing temperature progressively decreased by 1°C by cycle)
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 58°C 72°C	15 sec 30 sec 30 sec	
Extension		72°C	10 min	Extension

Table 4.3.4.6. nirK PCR cycling conditions

1. qPCR standard preparation

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 55°C 72°C	60 sec 60 sec 60 sec
Extension		72°C	10 min

Table 4.3.4.7. *nifH* PCR cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 57°C 72°C	60 sec 2 min 2 min
Extension		72°C	10 min

Table 4.3.4.8. *cbbL* PCR cycling conditions

1. qPCR standard preparation

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 56°C 72°C	10 sec 30 sec 30 sec
Extension		72°C	10 min

Table 4.3.4.9. GH7 PCR cycling conditions

1. qPCR standard preparation

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	15 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	30	95°C 56°C 72°C	15 sec 30 sec 30 sec
Melt curve	1	65-95°C	2-5 sec/step*

Table 4.3.4.12. Inhibition test qPCR cycling conditions

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	15 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 57°C 72°C	60 sec 2 min 2 min
Extension	1	72°C	10 min

Table 12: cbbL PCR cycling conditions

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	15 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 56°C 72°C	10 sec 30 sec 30 sec
Extension	1	72°C	10 min

Table 13: GH7 PCR cycling conditions

The expected size of the qPCR standard amplicons (PCR products from the above reactions) is verified by electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel in TBE buffer stained with SYBR Safe® DNA gel stain. Amplicons are purified with NucleoMag® NGS Bead Suspension according to the manufacturer instructions and quantified with Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit following the manual. Make sure you get at least 10 ng/μl of PCR product.

2. Cloning of qPCR standard

 The ligation should be started the same day after purifying the PCR product obtained in the PCR reactions mentioned above (Tables 4.3.4.3 to 4.3.4.9.). If the PCR product is stored, the A-Overhangs left by the polymerase may detach from the product and ligation efficiency will decrease.

 The ligation is made using the pGEM®-T Easy Vector Systems kit from Promega, following the manufacturer's instructions but incubating the ligation reaction overnight instead of for a few hours.

 Transform your competent cells (10⁸ cfu/μg DNA) provided with the kit, with the ligation mixture following the kit's instructions and plate 100 μL aliquots of the cells suspension onto LB/Amp/IPTG/X-Gal solid medium. Incubate the Petri dishes at 37°C overnight in the dark for no more than 13 h. This process will facilitate the white or blue colour development of the colonies.

For screening of the recombinant clone, pick three white colonies per GOI (colonies containing the PCR product) and a blue one. Transfer them to liquid LB media with Ampicillin and incubate overnight at 37°C.

 Extract the plasmid using the Isolate II Plasmid Mini Kit from Bioline.

 To ensure you get the desired product size, run a test PCR for each GOI's white and blue colonies using the primers listed in Table 4.3.4.1. with the reaction mixture of Table 4.3.4.2 and the cycling conditions described in Tables 4.3.4.3 to 4.3.4.9.

 Quantify the plasmids with Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit.

3. qPCR standard curve

The qPCR standard curve is performed on a serial dilution of the standard plasmid ranging from 10⁸ to 10¹ copies per reaction. The GOI is amplified using the specific primers pair listed in Table 4.3.4.1., the reaction mixture described in Table 4.3.4.10, and the cycling program described in Tables 4.3.4.3. to 4.3.4.9. The final extension was replaced by a dissociation stage (melt analysis) by gradually increasing the temperature from 60°C to 95°C. Standard dilutions and non-template controls (NCT) made of molecular-grade water should be amplified in triplicate.

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (µL)	Final Conc.
SYBR Green®	2x	10	1x
BSA	20 mg/mL	0.6	0.6 mg/mL
Forward Primer	10 µM	0.8	400 nM
Reverse Primer	10 µM	0.8	400 nM
Plasmid standard	***	2	***
Sterile H2O	***	5.8	***
Total Volume		20	

Table 14: qPCR reaction mixture

At the end of the assay, the results are analysed using the automatic option of the thermocycler. The qPCR is validated with the following observations:

- (1) no amplification in NTC reactions,
- (2) a single dissociation peak for each dilution of the qPCR standard,
- (3) a linear calibration curve (standard curve) with $R_2 \geq 98\%$.

3. qPCR standard curve

The qPCR calibration curve gives the number of cycle thresholds (Ct) as a function of the amount of the log of the number of copies of standard sequences. The efficiency of the qPCR assay, which is calculated by the thermocycler software, is estimated from the calibration curve formula:

$$Ct = \alpha \times q + c$$

"Ct" is measured cycle threshold;

" α " is the slope of the calibration curve;
"q" is the log copy number of the qPCR standard;

"c" is the ordinate at the origin (Ct for 1 copy of qPCR standard).

$$E = 10^{(-1/\alpha)} - 1$$

where E is the efficiency of the calibration assay and α is the slope of the calibration curve.

It shall be stated that a calibration curve having a slope equal to -3.32 is 100 % efficient. Therefore, a 10-fold-dilution of a given DNA template gives a Ct difference of 3.32 for a qPCR assay 100 % efficient (i.e. if 10^8 Ct = 10, so 10^7 Ct = 13.32).

4. DNA inhibition test

Inhibition in qPCR occurs when components used in qPCR hinder the activity of the (Taq) polymerase. Such a component is the intercalating fluorescent dye SYBR Green® itself used in qPCR. However, inhibition in qPCR usually refers to impurities, such as humic acid substances, co-purified with sample nucleic acids. These impurities may have an impact on PCR efficiency, thus delaying the amplification and, therefore, decreasing the sample copy number in absolute quantification. Inhibition is tested in the following way:

- Spike 10⁴ copies of plasmid DNA to soil DNA and perform a qPCR using SP6 and T7 primers.
- The amplification reaction is performed with the reaction mixture described in Table 4.3.4.10 including the soil DNA dilutions to be tested, three positive controls containing only plasmid DNA, and three NTC. The qPCR cycling program is shown in the following table and it will include a final dissociation stage (melt analysis).

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	15 min
Denaturation Annealing Extension	30	95°C 55°C 72°C	15 sec 30 sec 30 sec
Melt curve	1	65-95°C	2-5 sec/step*

Table 15: Inhibition test qPCR cycling conditions

The inhibition test is validated by observing the following:

- no amplification for NTC,
- similar Ct values in qPCR performed from spiked soil DNA extract and plasmid only DNA.

Soil DNA dilution showing no inhibition is chosen as the template to perform the qPCR assay.

5. qPCR assays

Once we have developed a proper standard curve and obtained a DNA template free of inhibitors, the qPCR assay can be run for our DNA samples extracted from soil according to chapter 4.3.1 of this Handbook. 10⁸ to 10¹ dilutions of the standard plasmid are run in every qPCR assay to create the standard curve and obtain absolute quantification. The qPCR assay targeting the GOI will be performed on each soil DNA template at the dilution, showing no inhibition precisely as described in “3. qPCR standard curve”, with the only difference that both standards and DNA templates will be performed in duplicate.

Calculations

In this section, the calculation of the copy number of the GOI in the soil DNA extract is described. The calibration curve and qPCR efficiency shall be calculated for each assay and recorded with the estimated number of copies of the GOI. The copy number of GOI can be calculated to the copy number per ng of soil DNA or per g of soil with the following formulas:

- Estimation of the number of sequences of the GOI per ng of soil DNA

$$I \text{ (GOI/ng DNA)} = \frac{\text{GOI in assay}}{\text{volume of template in assay } (\mu\text{L}) \times \text{concentration of template in assay } (\text{ng}/\mu\text{L})}$$

- Estimation of the number of sequences of the GOI per g of soil (II)

$$II \text{ (GOI/g soil)} = \frac{I \times \text{extracted DNA from soil (ng)}}{\text{soil sample from which DNA is extracted (in g of dry mass equivalent)}}$$

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3.3 Soil DNA extraction and purification

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Principle & Application

To obtain DNA for subsequent amplicon sequencing, soil DNA will be extracted using the commercial kit DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) and purified using NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select magnetic beads (Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany).

These steps will follow the manufacturer's instructions except for the modifications described hereunder.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

1. Gloves
2. Analytical balance
3. Spatula
4. Oven
5. Water bath
6. Centrifuge
7. Pipettes
8. Filtered tips
9. Vortex
10. Lysing Matrix E tubes
11. MP FastPrep-24 instrument
12. Microcentrifuge tubes*
13. MB Spin Columns*
14. Collection tubes*
15. Elution tubes*
16. Low DNA binding thin-walled 0.2mL PCR tubes
17. 0.2 ml PCR tube
18. Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer
19. Low DNA binding thin-walled 0.5mL Eppendorfs PCR tubes
20. NanoDrop 2000c spectrophotometer

Reagents

- Ice
- DNase away or 70% ethanol
- Solutions CD1, CD2, CD3, EA, C5, and C6*
- Distilled water
- Invitrogen™ Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit
- NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select beads
- Fresh 80% ethanol
- 1x TE buffer

Procedure

Before starting, thoroughly wipe down with DNase away or 70% ethanol the benchtop, tip racks, pipettes, centrifuge, vortex, etc., and set the centrifuge at 15-25°C. All centrifugation steps will be performed at room temperature. If Solution CD3 has precipitated, heat it at 60°C until the precipitate dissolves.

DNA Extraction:

- Spin down the Lysing Matrix E tubes (MP Biomedicals, Solon, OH, USA).
- To the Lysing Matrix E tubes, add 0.25 grams of soil sample.
- Add 800 µl of solution CD1.
- Vortex briefly to mix.
- Heat the Lysing Matrix E tubes in a water bath at 65°C for 5 minutes and at 1000 rpm.

- Secure the Lysing Matrix E tubes in the MP FastPrep-24 instrument (MP Biomedicals, Solon, OH, USA), and perform the bead-beating step at 5.5 m s⁻¹ for 30 seconds for a total of two shakes.
- Centrifuge the Lysing Matrix E tubes at 15,000 x g for 5 minutes.
- Transfer the supernatant to a clean 2 ml Microcentrifuge tube.
- Note: expect 500–600 µl. The supernatant may still contain some soil particles.
- Add 200 µl of solution CD₂.
- Vortex for 5 seconds.

- Centrifuge the tubes at 15,000 x g for 1 minute.
- Avoiding the pellet, transfer up to 700 µl of supernatant to a clean 2 ml Microcentrifuge tube.
- Note: Expect 500–600 µl.
- Add 600 µl of solution CD₃.
- Vortex for 5 seconds.
- Load 650 µl of the lysate onto an MB Spin Column.
- Note: Be careful not to overload the column.
- Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 minute.
- Discard the flow-through.
- Note: Solution CD₃ contains guanidinium thiocyanate and should not enter drains, water courses, or the soil; dispose of it appropriately.
- Repeat step 15 to ensure all the lysate has passed through the MB Spin Column.
- Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 2 minutes.
- Carefully place the MB Spin Column into a clean 2 ml Collection tube.
- Note: avoid splashing any flow-through onto the MB Spin Column.

- Add 500 µl of solution EA to the MB Spin Column.
- Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 minute.
- Discard the flow-through and place the MB Spin Column back into the same 2 ml Collection tube.
- Add 500 µl of solution C₅ to the MB Spin Column.
- Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 minute.
- Discard the flow-through and place the MB Spin Column into a new 2 ml Collection tube.
- Centrifuge at up to 16,000 x g for 2 minutes.
- Carefully place the MB Spin Column into a new 1.5 ml Elution tube.
- Add 60 µl of Solution C₆ to the centre of the white filter membrane.
- Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 minute.
- Discard the MB Spin Column.

DNA Purification:

- Remove the NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select Bead Suspension (Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany) from the refrigerator and let stand for approximately 30 minutes to bring the bead suspension to room temperature.
- Gently shake the beads bottle until the suspension is homogeneous.

-
- In a 0.2 mL PCR tube, add x1.2 volume of the bead suspension to the DNA samples.
 - Mix thoroughly by pipetting up and down.
 - Incubate mixed samples for 10 minutes at room temperature for maximum recovery and tap gently every 2-3 minutes.
 - Place the tube onto the magnetic plate for 2 to 5 minutes to separate the beads from the solution.

Note: wait for the solution to be clear before proceeding to the next step.

- Remove the supernatant and discard.

Note: This step must be performed while the tubes are situated on the magnetic plate. If beads are drawn out, leave a few microlitres of supernatant behind.

- Add 120µl of fresh 80% ethanol to the 0.2 ml tube on the magnetic plate.
- Incubate for 1 minute at room temperature.

-
- Pipette off the ethanol (supernatant) and discard.
 - Repeat steps 8 to 10 for a total of 2 washes.

Note: It is important to perform these steps with the tubes situated on the magnetic plate. Do not disturb the separated magnetic beads, and be sure to remove all the ethanol from the bottom of the tube, as it is known as a PCR inhibitor.

- Open the tube lids to evaporate off the excess of ethanol (≤ 5 minutes).

Note: Take care not to over dry the beads as this will significantly decrease elution efficiency.

DNA Purification:

- Remove the tubes from the magnetic plate.
- Add 30 to 50 μ l of elution buffer (1x TE).
- Mix by pipetting up and down to separate the beads from the DNA.

Note: The liquid level must be high enough to contact the magnetic beads. A lower volume might require extra mixing and may not fully elute the entire product. Elution is relatively rapid, and the beads don't need to go back into solution for it to occur.

- Place the tubes back onto the magnetic plate for 1 minute to separate the beads from the solution.
 - Transfer the eluent to a new tube. This contains the purified DNA.
-

Determination of DNA quantity using Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer

- Prepare High Sensitive (HS) standards and DNA samples according to the manual supplied by the Invitrogen™ Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit.
- Calibrate the Qubit® 2.0 (Fluorometer Life Technologies, Carlsbad, California, US) according to the manual using the prepared HS standards.
- Measure the DNA concentration in all samples according to the Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer manual.

Determination of DNA quality using NanoDrop 2000c

1. Make sure the measuring arm on the Nanodrop apparatus (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, US) is in a down position.
2. Open the ND-1000 program by double-clicking on the NanoDrop ND1000 icon.
3. Choose "Nucleic Acid measurements" and "DNA".

- Lift the measuring arm on the apparatus and remove the tissue paper;
- Check that both measuring surfaces are clean (if not, then clean them with a soft piece of paper);
- Apply 1.5 μ l of MQ water;
- Close the measuring arm.

4. Click "OK".

To calibrate:

- Lift the measuring arm;
- Clean the measuring surface with a soft piece of paper (Kleenex);
- Apply 1.5 μ l of solution C6 as a blank and close the measuring arm;
- Click on "blank".

To measure the DNA quality:

- Lift the measuring arm;
- Clean the measuring surface with a soft piece of paper;
- Apply 1.5 μl of the extracted DNA sample and close the measuring arm;
- Write the sample name in the field on the right-hand side of the screen;
- Click on "measure";
- Write down the measured concentration (or print a report after the last sample);
- Repeat steps a) to f) for all samples.

The DNA is now ready for downstream applications and should be stored frozen (-80°C).

Calculations

The Qubit 2.0 software calculates the DNA concentration of all samples.

The quality of the DNA is determined by the $A_{260}/_{280}$ and $A_{260}/_{230}$ ratios quantified by the NanoDrop software.

Remarks

DNA quantity and quality are crucial in metagenomics studies. Low DNA yield or poor DNA quality will likely lead to an inaccurate estimation of microbial diversity (Inceoşlu et al., 2010). DNA $260/_{280}$ and $260/_{230}$ ratios should be higher than >1.8 to avoid this. At the same time, the quantified DNA should have a minimum concentration of 10 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{l}$ with at least 200 ng and should be resuspended in water, 10 mM Tris Hcl pH 8.5 or TE buffer (although water should be avoided to prevent acid hydrolysis).

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3.4 Bacterial and archaeal genetic diversity: ssu rRNA gene amplicon sequencing

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Principle & Application

Small subunit (ssu) rRNA amplicon sequencing is a widely used high throughput method to identify microbial species in different environments, allowing for cultivation-independent determination of microbial community composition (Caporaso et al., 2012).

The technique is based on PCR amplification of hypervariable regions of the ssu rRNA gene (also termed 16S rRNA gene in bacteria), which are then analysed using Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology and compared against microbial databases to determine the identity and abundance of microbial taxa. Within the SoildiverAgro Project, UCPH has opted to use a commercial next-generation sequencing provider for our sequencing needs to enhance our ability to meet tight deadlines for our project deliverables.

Procedure

- For amplicon sequencing, send the high-quality DNA samples obtained by DNA extraction (minimum concentration of 10 ng/uL) to NOVOGENE (HK) COMPANY LIMITED.
- At Novogene, PCR amplification will be conducted using the modified bacterial/archaeal primer pair 515F -GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA and 806R-GGACTACNVGGGTWTCTAAT targeting the V4 region of the bacterial 16s rRNA gene (Parada et al., 2016; Walters et al., 2016).
- The PCR products will subsequently be purified and used for library preparation.
- The prepared library will be sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq2500 platform, and 250-bp paired-end reads will be generated with at least 50,000 raw reads per sample (Q30 \geq 75%).
- The obtained reads will subsequently be quality-checked and analysed using the following methods and software:

Procedure

Standard Analysis	Software
Data split and reads merging	FLASH
Data quality control: data filtration and chimera removal	QIIME
OTUs(Operational Taxonomic Units) Clustering and Species annotation, including OTUs Heatmap, GraPhlAn display, Taxonomy Tree, KRONA results	Uparse, PyNast, Mothur
Species distribution, including Ternary plot, Species Abundance Heatmap, and the evolutionary tree in genus.	RDP
Alpha-diversity Analysis, including Alpha Indices table(Observed species, Good's coverage, Chao1, ACE, Shannon, Simpson, PD whole tree), Species diversity curves, Species accumulation boxplot, Venn and Flower diagram(Up to 5 figures for free)	QIIME, R
Beta-diversity Analysis, including Beta diversity heatmap, (un)weighted unifracs distance analysis, PCA (Principal Component Analysis), PCoA (Principal Co-ordinates Analysis), UPGMA (Unweighted Pair-group Method with Arithmetic Means), MetaStat, LefSe analysis	QIIME, R

Table 16: Procedure - bacterial and archaeal genetic diversity: ssu rRNA gene amplicon sequencing

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3.5 Fungal/Mycorrhiza genetic diversity: Fungal ITS Illumina amplicon sequencing

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Principle & Application

Amplicon sequencing is a highly targeted approach that enables the analysis of genetic variation in specific genomic regions. This method, which employs DNA metabarcoding, allows the paralleled amplification and sequencing of potentially thousands of different barcoded regions belonging to other species. The barcoded region corresponds to a short fragment within an organism's genome, whose sequence is conserved within a species but varies among different species. By comparing the sequences obtained to those of a reference database, it is possible to gather information about the community composition of a complex sample. The ultra-deep sequencing of PCR products (amplicons) allows efficient variant identification and characterisation. Illumina amplicon sequencing uses oligonucleotide probes designed to target and capture regions of interest, followed by next-generation sequencing (NGS).

NGS overcomes the limits of the cultivation-based methods and allows profiling the entire microbiome by directly sequencing the DNA taken from a wide range of different and complex samples.

In this protocol, we chose the fungal Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region for fungal amplicon sequencing. ITS is part of the non-transcriptional region of the fungal rRNA gene. The ITS sequences used for fungal identification usually include ITS1 and ITS2 because 5.8S, 18S, and 28S rRNA genes are highly conserved in fungi. In contrast, ITS can tolerate more mutations in the evolutionary process and exhibits extensive sequence polymorphism in most eukaryotes. At the same time, the conservative type of ITS is relatively consistent within species; the differences between species are easily detectable, and they have been widely used in phylogenetic analysis of different fungi (Kim et al. 2013).

In this protocol, the Illumina MiSeq system, with a read length of 2 x 300 bp and an output of 22-25 M reads, was chosen to characterise the fungal diversity. Illumina sequencing by synthesis (SBS) chemistry is the most widely adopted NGS technology, generating approximately 90% of global sequencing data (Illumina 2015).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Pipettes and pipette tips
- PE test tubes
- Fume hood cabinet
- Horizontal electrophoresis system
- PCR System
- Fluorometer to quantify double-strand DNA (i.e. Qubit, Thermo Fisher Scientific)
- Illumina MiSeq sequencer
- Oligonucleotides used as PCR primers purified with standard desalting
- Taq polymerase (or commercial kit)
- Deoxynucleotide solution, dNTPs
- Magnesium chloride, $MgCl_2$ (CAS No. 7786-30-3)
- Molecular-biology-grade water, H_2O
- DNA ladder with known lengths and concentrations of fragments
- GreenSafe (NZYTech)
- Mag-Bind RXNPure Plus magnetic beads (Omega Biotek)
- Tris-HCl, 1 mol/L, 121.14 g of Tris in 1000 mL of H_2O , adjusting with 4 mol/L HCl to pH 8.0.
- TE buffer × 10: pH 8.0, 100 mL of 1 mol/L Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 20 mL of 50 mmol/L EDTA pH 8.0 in 880 mL of molecular grade water.

Procedure

Amplicon library preparation

This protocol is based on the protocol described in the Earth Microbiome Project (<http://www.earthmicrobiome.org/protocols-and-standards/its/>). The libraries are prepared following a 2-step PCR protocol. For the first PCR, the fungal ITS1- ITS2 region with an amplicon of ~450 bp (Bokulich and Mills 2013; Hoggard et al. 2018) is amplified using the primers ITS1f (5' - CTTGGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA - 3') (Gardes and Bruns 1993) and ITS2 primer (5' - GCTGCGTTCTTCATCGATGC - 3') (White et al. 1990). These primers include an oligonucleotide extension at their respective 5' ends to make the amplicons suitable for sequencing in an Illumina MiSeq sequencer.

The complete primer sequences are shown in Table 4.3.3.1. The reaction mixture and the cycling conditions of the first PCR are described in table 4.3.3.2. and 4.3.3.3, respectively. The indices required for multiplexing different samples in the same sequencing run will be added in a second PCR with identical conditions but with only 5 cycles and 60 °C as the annealing temperature. Figure 4.3.3.1. depicts a schematic overview of the library preparation process (Vierna et al. 2017).

Procedure

PCR #	Primer name	Primer sequence (5' - 3')*	Reference
PCR1	ITS1f	ACACTCTTTCCCTACA CGACGCTCTTCCGATC TCTTGGTCATTTAGAG GAAGTAA	Gardes and Bruns 1993
PCR1	ITS2	GTGACTGGAGTTCAGA CGTGTGCTCTTCCGAT CTGCTGCGTTCTTCAT CGATGC	White et al. 1990
PCR2	Forward primer	AATGATACGGCGACCA COGAGATCTACACNNN NNNNNACACTCTTTCC CTACACGA	
PCR2	Reverse primer	CAAGCAGAAGACGGC ATACGAGATNNNNNN NNGTGACTGGAGTTCA GACGTG	

Table 17: PCR primers

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (ul)	Final Conc.
Supreme NZY TM aq 2x Green Master Mix (NZY TM Tech)	2x	12.5	1x
Forward Primer	10 uM	1.25	500 nM
Reverse Primer	10 uM	1.25	500 nM
DNA template	***	2.5	***
Sterile H ₂ O	***	7.5	***
Total volume		25	

Table 18: PCR reaction mixture

Procedure

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	2x 10 uM 10 uM *** ***	12.5 1.25 1.25 2.5 7.5	1x 500 nM 500 nM *** ***
Denaturation Annealing Extension	35	95°C 52°C 68°C	30 sec 30 sec 30 sec
Extension		68°C	10 min

Figure: Schematic representation of the primers used for PCR1 and PCR2 (Adapted from Vierna et al. 2017)

Procedure

A negative control containing no DNA must be included in every PCR round to check for contamination during the library preparation (BPCR).

The libraries are verified by electrophoresis on 2 % agarose gel stained with GreenSafe (NZYTech) and imaged under UV light to confirm the library size.

The libraries are purified using the Mag-Bind RXNPure Plus magnetic beads (Omega Biotek), following the instructions provided by the manufacturer. Then, they will be pooled in equimolar amounts according to the quantification data supplied by the Qubit dsDNA HS Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

High-throughput sequencing

The pool will be sequenced in a MiSeq PE300 run (Illumina). The MiSeq run includes a 5-10 % control PhiX library (Illumina) to increase the sequence diversity among amplicons.

REMARKS

DNA quantity and quality are crucial in metagenomics studies. Low DNA yield or poor DNA quality will likely lead to an inaccurate estimation of microbial diversity (Claassen et al. 2013; Ínceoşlu et al. 2010). To avoid this, DNA 260/280 and 260/230 ratios should be higher than >1.8 . At the same time, the quantified DNA should have a minimum concentration of 10 ng/ μ l with at least 200 ng and should be resuspended in water, 10mM Tris Hcl pH 8.5 or TE buffer (although water should be avoided to prevent acid hydrolysis).

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3.6 Protists genetic diversity and relative abundance: 18S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing

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Principle & Application

Although protists constitute the invisible majority of eukaryotes with a vast morphological and lifestyle diversity, they are still an often forgotten component of the soil microbiome (Geisen et al., 2018). Due to their predatory activity, protists release nutrients from their prey's biomass, making them available to plants and other organisms in their environment, playing an important role in shaping the dynamics of soil organisms (Bonkowski, 2004).

The development of new molecular markers and databases has provided new insight into the diversity and abundance of protists (Mahé et al., 2017). 18S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing has become a standard Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) method to assess soil microbial diversity. The sequences obtained by this high-throughput technology are then compared against reference databases to determine the identity and abundance of the amplified organisms.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- PCR Hood
- PCR thermocycler
- Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen™)
- Horizontal electrophoresis system
- Gel imaging system
- Cold well-loading block
- Pipettes
- Filtered tips
- Low DNA binding eppendorfs
- PCR tubes
- Illumina sequencer

- Oligonucleotides used as PCR primers purified with standard desalting
- Taq polymerase (or commercial kit)
- Deoxynucleotide solution, dNTPs
- Magnesium chloride, MgCl₂ (CAS No. 7786-30-3)
- Molecular-biology-grade water, H₂O
- Agarose
- DNA ladder with known lengths and concentrations of fragments
- GreenSafe (NZYTech)
- Mag-Bind RXNPure Plus magnetic beads (Omega Biotek)
- 10mM Tris-HCl
- TE buffer

REAGENTS

Procedure

High-quality soil DNA extracted and purified according to the method described in Chapter XX of this Handbook (minimum concentration of 10 ng/ μ L) will be sent for amplicon sequencing.

At the sequencing facility, a PCR amplification will be conducted using the primer set Euk1391f (5' – GTACACACCGCCCGTC – 3') (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2009) and EukBr (5' – TGATCCTTCTGCAGGTTACCTAC – 3') (Stoeck et al., 2010), targeting the V9 region of the 18S rRNA gene. These primers include an oligonucleotide extension at their respective 5' ends to make the amplicons suitable for sequencing in an Illumina sequencer. A negative control containing no DNA will be included in every PCR round to check for contamination during library preparation.

The resulting PCR products will be verified by electrophoresis on 2 % agarose gel stained with GreenSafe (NZYTech) and imaged under UV light to confirm the library size.

The libraries will then be purified using the Mag-Bind RXNPure Plus magnetic beads (Omega Biotek), following the manufacturer's instructions. Then, they will be pooled in equimolar amounts according to the quantification data supplied by the Qubit dsDNA HS Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

The pool will be sequenced on a NovaSeq PE250 run (Illumina), and 250-bp paired-end reads will be generated with an average of 100k raw reads per sample. The run includes a 5-10 % control PhiX library (Illumina) to increase the sequence diversity among amplicons.

The obtained reads will be subsequently quality-checked and analysed using a combination of bioinformatics tools.

REMARKS

DNA quantity and quality are crucial in metagenomics studies. Low DNA yield or poor DNA quality will likely lead to an inaccurate estimation of microbial diversity (Inceoşlu et al., 2010). To avoid this, DNA 260/280 and 260/230 ratios should be higher than >1.8 . At the same time, the quantified DNA should have a minimum concentration of 10 ng/ μ l with at least 200 ng and should be resuspended in water, 10mM Tris Hcl pH 8.5 or TE buffer (although water should be avoided to prevent acid hydrolysis).

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3.7 Excrement baits as a proxy for coprophagous fauna activity

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Principle & Application

Coprophagous fauna involves different insect taxa, notably Diptera and Coleoptera. Beetle coprophagous are particularly sensitive to animal management perturbations, as some guilds filtrate microbes from excrement moisture. When specific sanitary treatments are introduced in an animal farm, Coleoptera is severely affected due to both disturbances in their microbial food source and ecotoxicity.

Coprophagous beetle assemblages can be studied through pitfall traps, albeit baited with excrements around the trap or suspended directly above. However, measuring the weight variation of baited excrements during short periods in the highest activity season of these insects is a proxy for the community's total activity and, thus, their ecological functionality (related to carbon cycling, decomposition, and excrement parasite proliferation).

Equipment & Material

- A plastic barrel
- Hoe or spade
- Scale (0,1 to 1g sensibility)
- Paper bags
- Plastic sealable bags
- Colour flags (optional)
- Laboratory incineration equipment

Procedure

- Collect fresh excrement from any type of animal (from the same day). Cattle dung is suggested due to its abundance and ease of manipulation. The excrement source must not contain ivermectin or other eco-toxic substances.
- Thoroughly homogenise the excrements.
- Prepare a 100 g ball of excrement per bait.
- In each study site, place from 10 to 20 excrement baits separated at least 2 meters from each other. Mark their location and place bright, colourful flags to help recover them later.
- Keep at least 400 to 1kg of fresh excrement and store it in a paper bag inside a sealed plastic bag.
- Return after seven days and retrieve the baits. Record the weight of each bait and place them in paper bags inside sealed plastic bags. Label the collected baits and record the retrieval date.
- At the laboratory, dry the samples at 70°C for 48 hours and weigh them.
- Compare the difference between the exposed baits' initial and final dry weight, using the separated 400g as the blank sample.

Remarks

Special caution must be taken if excrements are transferred from one farm to another due to sanitary risks.

Excrements must be placed while fresh, meaning that ideally, they should be placed on the same day as they were collected and, in the worst scenario, one day later.

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3.8 Pitfall traps for soil epigeal fauna

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Principle & Application

This methodology involves taking several soil samples from your selected point or homogeneous area and mix them together to obtain a composite sample to take to the laboratory for DNA extraction. This ensures an adequate representativeness of the area and a reduction of the possible variability that may exist between samples from the same point.

By DNA metabarcoding, it will be possible to obtain not only the arthropod species present in each soil sample, but also the arthropod species that have passed through that soil (and left traces) during the last 7 days (approximately). This is a very efficient and non-invasive methodology for arthropods.

The IBS (Soil Biodiversity Index) is founded on a presence/absence matrix of indicative ecomorphological taxa. Each taxon presents a different ecomorphological score based on its value of soil ecological function, response to disturbance, role in the trophic chain, and relation to other relevant species (umbrella species).

Equipment & Material

- Soil auger (min. 2 cm diameter)
- ZIP bags
- Eding marker
- Refrigerator with ice plates
- Bucket
- Hoe
- Scale
- Gloves

Procedure

- At each sampling point take three soil samples 1 m apart. Once selected, the first 5-10 cm of the soil should be excavated to remove the layer of organic matter and possible vegetation present.
- Subsequently, the soil auger is introduced and approximately 100 cm³ are obtained from each of them.
- In the bucket, mix and homogenise the soil samples and take 300 g in a correctly labelled ZIP bag.
- Put the bag in the refrigerator with the ice plates for its correct preservation and send it to the laboratory within 1-2 days.
- From the laboratory results note the presence or absence of each faunal taxon.

Remarks

This methodology should be done in those seasons with the highest activity of the edaphofauna and rainy days should be avoided (so that soil samples can be easily collected). In clayey or compacted soils, it is difficult to extract the soil with the soil auger.

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04 SOIL FERTILITY AND POLLUTION ASSESSMENT

4.1 Soil pH

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Principle & Application

The pH is the negative logarithm of the concentration of hydrogen ions expressed in mol L⁻¹. The pH of a soil is conditioned by the base-forming cations (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na²⁺ and K⁺) and by the acid-forming cations (Fe²⁺ or Fe³⁺, H⁺ y Al³⁺) (Mccauley, Jones, and Olson-Rutz 2017).

The pH is a fundamental property in the study of soils since it determines solubility, concentration in solution, mobility and ionic form of nutrients (Fageria and Nascente 2014), and, therefore, their availability (Horrocks and Vallentine 1999).

Some elements, such as nitrogen, iron or copper, are more available at acidic pHs, and others, such as calcium, magnesium, and sodium, are easily washable at acidic pH and are more available in basic soils.

Figure

Figure: Effect of the soil pH in the availability of some nutrients. The wider the blue line, the more available the element (Roques et al. 2013)

There are some crops develop correctly with a pH range in water of 6-7 (Daniels 2016), while others prefer more acidic soils (Miller 2016). Usually, a 1:5 soil suspension in water is used to measure soil pH (Ditzler, Scheffe, and Monger 2017). However, certain electrolytes can also be used for different purposes. Suppose a 0.01M solution of calcium chloride (CaCl_2) is used instead of water. In that case, the seasonal variation can be dampened: the pH, in this case, depends very little on the initial saline concentration. The use of potassium chloride (KCl) is also common since this electrolyte displaces the remaining H^+ and Al^{3+} cations in the exchange complex, causing them to reach the solution and decreasing the measured pH (Kome et al. 2018). Therefore, the pH in KCl is related to the saturation of the exchange complex by aluminium.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Balance
- Greiner tubes of 15mL
- Spatula
- Shaker
- Distilled water
- Potassium Chloride (KCl)
- Calcium Chloride (CaCl_2)
- pH-meter
- Buffers (pH 4, 7 and 9.21)

Procedure

The procedure to measure pH is as follows:

- Weigh 2 g of soil (sieved, 2 mm).
- Add 10 mL of distilled water.
- Shake for 1 h.
- Let the suspension rest for 1 h.
- Calibrate the pH meter with 4.0, 7.0 and 9.21 standards
- Measure in pH-meter before 2 h.

The procedure is repeated twice, replacing the water with a 1M solution of KCl and a 0.01 M solution of CaCl₂, always maintaining the same proportion (1:5).

Calculations

The difference between the pH in KCl and the pH in H₂O ($\Delta\text{pH} = \text{pH KCl} - \text{pH H}_2\text{O}$) is calculated to determine if the soil has cation exchange capacity (the difference is negative) or if the soil has an anion exchange capacity (this difference is positive) (Kome et al. 2018).

Remarks

When you start to measure pH (or when the pH change from one sample to the next is very pronounced), it is advisable to measure the pH continuously for a few minutes and wait for the measurement to stabilise. It is possible to establish a correlation between the organic matter content of a soil and its pH in CaCl₂ (Fuentes et al. 2019).

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4.2 Electrical conductivity

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Principle & Application

The salinity of soil is the amount of dissolved salts present in the aqueous phase of that soil (Kalev and Toor, 2018). These salts affect water movement, soil structure, and microbial and plant diversity (Artiola et al., 2019). For example, a high concentration of salts can limit the growth of crops. Salinisation is the high concentration of salts in the soil. It can occur for various reasons, for example, the lack of rainfall, a water table near the surface that evaporates quickly, or the use of irrigation water with high salt content. It is estimated that 7% of the Earth's area presents salinity problems (Gupta and Abrol, 1990). Furthermore, it is a growing problem that can already be favoured by the increase in global mean temperature caused by climate change and by the rise of salinity in water resources (McFarlane and Williamson, 2002).

Therefore, the concentration of salts in the soil and ions in the solution is related to electrical conductivity (EC): soil suspensions with more ions can conduct an electric current more easily. For this reason, the method for determining soil salinity is based on the standard method for measuring electrical conductivity (Soil Science Division Staff, 2017).

Based on conductivity, a classification of soils can be made: those soils with a conductivity less than 2 dS m⁻¹ are considered non-saline, while those with a conductivity greater than 16 dS m⁻¹ are considered strongly saline.

Class	Electrical conductivity (dS/m)
0 Non Saline	0-2
1 Vry Slightly saline	2-4
2 Slightly saline	4-8
3 Moderately saline	8-16
4 Strongly saline	≥ 16

Table 19: Soil classification based on electrical conductivity (adapted from Soil Science Division Staff, 2017)

Equipment & Material

- Conductivity meter
- Beaker
- KCl standard solution 0.01 M (1412 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ at 25°C)
- Balance
- Pipette
- Stirrer

Procedure

The procedure is the following:

- Two grams of soil are weighed in a 25mL beaker;
 - 10 mL of distilled water is added;
 - The mixture is stirred for one hour;
 - The conductivity meter is calibrated with a 0.01 M KCl solution (with an electrical conductivity of 1412 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$);
 - The suspension is measured by introducing the conductivity electrode.
-

Calculations

A rough conversion (Hardie and Doyle, 2012) of electrical conductivity (in mS cm^{-1}) to total dissolved ions (TDI) can be done:

$$\text{TDI (mg L}^{-1}\text{)} = \text{CE (mS cm}^{-1}\text{)} \times 667$$

And to milliequivalents per litre:

$$\text{Meq L}^{-1} = \text{CE (mS cm}^{-1}\text{)} \times 10$$

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4.3 Total nitrogen

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Principle & Application

Nitrogen (N) is one of the essential elements for crop development, together with potassium (K) and phosphorus (P). N is distributed across the atmosphere, the biosphere and the lithosphere, but unlike K and P, N is not found in the rocks, so it must be introduced into the soil through fertilisation or the fixation of the atmospheric N₂ (Hofman and Cleemput, 2004). The total soil N content is usually between 0.05 and 0.2% by weight, but only a small proportion can be directly assimilated by plants that assimilate the inorganic N species ammonium or nitrate.

N deficiency is associated with lower crop yields and quality via reduced protein content (Dalal et al., 1991). There is a big difference in available N between different soils, as it is conditioned by many factors, including weather, season, depth, vegetation, crop history, slope, soil texture etc (Lin, 2006).

PRINCIPLE & APPLICATION

N deficiencies are common in unfertilised soils (Hofman and Cleemput, 2004), and it is therefore necessary to fertilise the soil providing this element. N fertilisation (in the form of synthetic fertilisers) in intensive agriculture reaches 600 kg per hectare per year in the field, and about 2000 kg in the greenhouse (Escanhoela et al., 2019). It is also possible to provide N by using organic fertilisers or rotations with N-fixing legumes (Crews and Peoples, 2004). The bacteria symbiotically associated with the roots of legumes are a crucial part of the soil N cycle since they can fix atmospheric nitrogen. Total soil N can be determined by a CHN elemental analyzer. Soil samples are burned at high temperatures in order to liberate the nitrogen, hydrogen and carbon gases. The gases are separated, and the amount of nitrogen is measured through a thermal conductivity detector since the thermal conductivity varies from one element to another.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Elemental Analyzer
- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- Oven
- Spatulas
- Soil mill
- Tin capsules

PROCEDURE

The method used to determine the total nitrogen is the same as that used for soil carbon. About 50 mg of ground dry soil is weighed in tin capsules and measured with the Elemental Analyzer. The nitrogen standards are also weighed and analysed. The proportions obtained with this method have to be converted into grams of total nitrogen per kilogram of dry soil.

CALCULATIONS

The results of total nitrogen are obtained in percentage by weight (g of N in 100 grams of dry soil), a unit that can be converted to grams of N per kilogram of dry soil by multiplying by 10.

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4.4 Inorganic nitrogen (nitrates and ammonium)

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Principle & Application

Nitrogen is an essential component for the nutrition of plants and microorganisms. Most of the nitrogen in the soil is in organic forms, and only a small fraction is found in mineral forms that are directly usable by plants and microorganisms. The mineralisation process of organic nitrogen, necessary for its assimilation as a nutrient, occurs mainly through ammonification (organic nitrogen passes to ammonium) and nitrification (oxidation of ammonium released into nitrate).

Nitrates and ammonium extraction in soil samples is carried out with a saturated solution of potassium chloride (KCl) and subsequent measure using ion chromatography (nitrate) and visible spectrophotometry (ammonium) (Sempere et al. 1993; Kandeler and Gerber 1988; Keeny and Nelson 1982). The soil used to determine inorganic nitrogen has to be kept at 4°C at field-moist conditions to avoid nitrification and denitrification processes by air-drying. The sample is stored at 4°C if analysed within 3 days from sampling. Otherwise, it is stored at -20°C to avoid the loss of mineral N.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

Nitrate determination

- Precision balance.
- Plastic vials (50 mL).
- Volumetric flask (100 mL).
- Rotating plate.
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL).
- Centrifuge.
- Syringe filters (0.2 μm).
- Syringe (10 mL).
- Ion chromatography equipment.

Ammonium determination

- Precision balance.
- Plastic vials (50 mL).
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL).
- Volumetric flasks (100, 500 and 1000 mL).
- Plastic buckets (2.5 mL).
- Vortex shaker.
- Centrifuge.
- Automatic pipette (1-5 mL).
- Rotating plate.
- Visible / UV spectrophotometer.

REAGENTS

Nitrate determination

- Solution of potassium chloride (2 M KCl): dissolve 149 g of potassium chloride (KCl) in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O. Fill up to the final volume with deionised water.
- Stock or commercial nitrate solution (1000 mg L⁻¹ NO₃⁻).

Ammonium determination

- Solution of potassium chloride (2 M KCl): dissolve 149 g of potassium chloride (KCl) in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O.
- Fill up to the final volume with deionised water.
- Sodium hydroxide (0.3 M NaOH): dissolve 12 g of NaOH in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O. Fill up to the final volume with deionised water.
- Sodium salicylate solution: dissolve 85 g of sodium salicylate (C₇H₅NaO₃) and 600 mg of sodium nitroprusside (Na₂ [Fe (CN)₅ NO]). Fill up to 500 mL with deionised water. Store at 4°C.
- Salicylate-Na / NaOH solution: mix equal volumes of 0.3 M NaOH, sodium salicylate and deionised water (1: 1: 1). Prepare daily.
- Solution of sodium dichloro isocyanide (0.1% C₃Cl₂N₃NaO₃) (w:v): dissolve 0.1 g of sodium dichloro isocyanide in 100 mL of deionised water. Prepare daily.
- Ammonium stock solution (100 mg L⁻¹ NH₄⁺): dissolve 0.297 g of NH₄Cl in 1000 mL of 2M KCl.

Procedure

Ammonium determination

- Homogenize the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred in a refrigerator container.
- Weigh 2.5 g of sieved soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of the 2M KCl solution (soil / extractant ratio 1:10).
- Shake for 60 min on the rotating plate.
- Centrifuge the samples 2 min at 5000 rpm.
- Take a 5 mL aliquot of the supernatant from each sample. For samples with a high ammonium content, pipette 2.5 mL (in this case being the dilution factor 2). Pour the aliquot in a 10 mL test tube. Add 2.5 mL of deionized water to the test tube if 2.5 mL has been pipetted to have a final volume of 5 mL in all tubes.
- Prepare tubes to determine the calibration curve. The standards will have concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5 2.5 and 5 mg L⁻¹ of NH₄⁺, prepared from the stock solution of 100 mg NH₄⁺ L⁻¹ (Table 1). These standards should be performed with the 2M KCl solution. These concentrations will be the dependent variables and the corresponding absorbances will be the independent variables.
-

Nitrate determination

- Homogenise the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred to a refrigerator container.
 - Weigh 2.5 g of sieved field-moist soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of potassium chloride solution (2 M KCl) (soil/extractant ratio 1:10).
 - Shake for 60 min on the rotating plate.
 - Centrifuge the samples for 2 min at 5000 rpm. Filter supernatant using syringe filters.
 - The extract obtained is measured in the ion chromatography equipment.
 - Prepare a calibration curve from the NO₃⁻ stock solution.
-

NH ₄ standard concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	Stock Solution volume (mL)
0	0
0.5	0.05
1	0.10
1.5	0.15
2.5	0.25
5	0.5

Table 20: Preparation of standards from the 100 mg stock solution NH₄ + L-1 (Final volume of 10 mL).

- Pipette 5 mL of each previously prepared standard.
- Add 2.5 mL of Salicylate-Na/NaOH solution and 1 mL of 0.1% sodium dichloro isocyanide to all tubes.
- Cover, shake (using the vortex shaker), and let stand for 30 min in darkness.
- Then, turn on the spectrophotometer and adjust the wavelength (λ) to 690 nm. Perform the auto-zero with the 0 mg NH₄ + L-1 standard.
- Measure all standards, including 0 mg NH₄ + mL⁻¹, to perform the calibration curve in which the NH₄ + concentration of the samples and blanks will be calculated.
- Measure the absorbance of the samples in the spectrophotometer. If any sample gives an absorbance greater than the maximum value of the calibration curve, it is necessary to take less volume of supernatant to make a dilution (step 5).

CALCULATIONS

Nitrate determination

- $\text{NO}_3^- \text{ (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)} = (\text{C} \times \text{V} \times \text{df}) / \text{m}$
- C is the concentration of nitrate obtained from ion chromatography (mg L^{-1})
- V is the total volume of the added deionised water (25 mL)
- df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1
- m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture)

Ammonium determination

$$\text{NH}_4^+ \text{ (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)} = (\text{C} \times \text{V} \times \text{df}) / \text{m}$$

C is the concentration of NH_4^+ obtained from the spectrophotometer (mg L^{-1})

V is the total volume of the added deionised water (25 mL)

df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1
m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture)

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4.5 Available P in the soil (Bray / Olsen)

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Principle & p Application

Principle and Application

After nitrogen, phosphorus is the element that has the most weight in plant production (Kauffman 2002). It is a forming element of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), an energy storage molecule essential for life, and is also a component of DNA and RNA. In plants, it is a crucial element in development (a significant amount of phosphorus is needed for cell division), flowering, fruit ripening and photosynthesis (Weil and Brady 2017).

In nature, it has no significant presence and is usually found in ways crops cannot use. Intensive agriculture (without the addition of phosphorus) usually produces low-phosphorus soils, making it difficult for vegetation to develop. This type of soil remains unprotected from erosion, something that happens, for example, in Sub-Saharan Africa (Weil and Brady 2017).

It is also common to find the opposite scenario: agricultural systems that add more phosphorus than is removed with each harvest. In many cases, this phosphorus ends up in the waters of rivers and lakes, generating eutrophic environments and putting the drinking water supply at risk.

Phosphorus is not found in large quantities in the soil, and the forms that appear in the soil are not usually assimilable by plants. In addition, when fertilised with the phosphorus already solubilised (in slurries, for example), it insolubilises easily when it reaches the soil. This is one of the reasons why it is usually fertilised in excess.

When determining the available phosphorus, this element is extracted using one solution or another depending on the pH, and the content is analysed by colourimetry, using the ascorbic acid method (Murphy and Riley 1962). Depending on the pH of the soil, one or another extractant is usually used, which results in different techniques: for alkaline soil, the Olsen method is employed, and for neutral or acidic soils, the Bray II method is used (Dari et al. 2019).

InBestSoil

1. Olsen

Equipment and Material

- Magnetic stirrer
 - Shaker
 - Greiner tubes (50 mL)
 - Dispenser
 - Beakers
 - Balance
 - Centrifuge
 - 0.45 μm Filters
 - Sulphuric acid, H_2SO_4
 - Sodium hydroxide, NaOH
 - Sodium bicarbonate, NaHCO_3
 - p-Nitrofenol ($\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}$)
 - Ammonium molybdate [$(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \times 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$]
 - Potassium antimony tartrate [$(\text{K}(\text{SbO}) \times \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6 \times \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O})$]
 - Ascorbic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$)
 - Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4)
 - Spectrophotometer
-

Procedure

Ammonium determination

- Before starting, it is necessary to prepare several solutions:
- O1: Sulphuric acid solution 2.5 M. To prepare this solution, it is necessary to carefully add 140 mL of H₂SO₄ (with 96% purity) to a one-litre volumetric flask containing about 10 mL of water and dilute it to mark it with distilled water.
- O2: Sodium hydroxide solution 1M. For this, it is necessary to dissolve 40 mL of NaOH in distilled water. It is an exothermic solution, so it is required to stir and let it cool before completing the volume with water.
- O3: Sodium bicarbonate solution. In a volume close to one litre (\approx 0.8-0.9 L), dissolve 42 g of sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃). The pH of the solution is adjusted to 8.5 (adding drops of the O₂ solution) before completing the volume (1 L).
- O4: 0.25% solution of p-Nitrophenol. 0.25 g of p-Nitrofenol (NO₂C₆H₄OH) are weighed in a 100mL volumetric flask and diluted to mark with water.
- O5: Ammonium molybdate solution 40g L⁻¹. 40 g of ammonium molybdate [(NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄] are weighed, dissolved in distilled water and made up to 1000 mL.
- O6: Potassium antimony tartrate solution. This solution should contain 1 mg of antimony per millilitre, so 0.2728 g of potassium antimony tartrate [(K(SbO) × C₄H₄O₆ × ½ H₂O)] are dissolved in distilled water and made up to 100 mL.
- O7: Ascorbic acid solution 0.1 M. This solution must be prepared at the time of use. 1.76 g of ascorbic acid (C₆H₄O₆) are dissolved in water and made up to 100 mL.
- O8: Sulphomolybdic solution. This solution must be prepared at the time of use. It is necessary to mix 50 mL of O₁ solution, 15 mL of O₅, 30 mL of O₇ and 5 mL of O₆.
- Preparing a phosphorus stock solution to make the standards is also necessary. To prepare this solution, it is necessary to weigh 4.3938 g of KH₂PO₄ (dried at 40 °C), dissolve it in distilled water and make it up to 1000 mL. The phosphorus concentration in this solution is 1000 mg L⁻¹.

Determining phosphorus can be divided into two parts: extraction and measurement by colourimetry.

To carry out the phosphorus extraction, two grams of soil are weighed (m) in a 50 mL Greiner tube, and 40 mL of the O_3 solution is added (V_E). This is stirred for 30 minutes and filtered by $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$. It is important to make a blank without soil but follow the same steps.

For the determination by colourimetry, an aliquot of the extract is taken (the volume of this aliquot depends on the amount of P the soil has, V_S), and 5 drops of O_4 are added. Then, O_1 is added until the colour changes to yellow. This is diluted with a bit of water and 8 mL of O_8 are added. In the end, the volume of 50 mL is completed with distilled water, let it stand for 10 min and measured with a spectrophotometer, using a wavelength of 882 nm.

When measuring, it is necessary to employ the same procedure with the standards that will be used in the calibration, replacing the soil or blank with a known concentration of phosphorus. Patterns of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mg L^{-1} are usually employed.

Calculations

$$C_p = (A - B) \frac{V_E}{V_S} \frac{50}{m}$$

The phosphorus content is usually referenced to grams of dry soil to present the results. For this, we can use the following formula:

Where:

C_p is the extractable phosphorus content in the soil (in mg of P g^{-1} of dry soil)

A is the P concentration in the sample (mg mL^{-1})

B is the P concentration in the blank (mg mL^{-1})

V_E is the volume of extractant used (mL).

V_S is the volume of sample measured by colourimetry (mL).

m is the soil mass (g)

2. Bray I

Equipment and Material

- Magnetic stirrer
 - Shaker
 - Greiner tubes (50 mL)
 - Dispenser
 - Beakers
 - Balance
 - Centrifuge
 - 0.45 μm Filters
 - Sulphuric acid, H_2SO_4
 - p-Nitrofenol ($\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}$)
 - Ammonium molybdate ($(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}$)
 - Potassium antimony tartrate ($\text{K}_2\text{Sb}_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_2\text{O}_6)_2$)
 - Ascorbic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$)
 - Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4)
 - Hydrochloric Acid (HCl)
 - Ammonium fluoride (NH_4F)
 - Boric acid (H_3BO_3)
 - Ammonia (NH_3)
 - Spectrophotometer
-

Procedure

Before starting, it is necessary to prepare several solutions:

- B1. Extraction solution of hydrochloric acid (0.1 N) and ammonium fluoride (0.03 N). Add 1.11 g of NH_4F and 8.28 mL of HCl (37%) to a 1 L volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.
- B2. This solution is done by mixing two solutions. The first one is done by diluting 0.116 g of potassium antimony tartrate in 500 mL of distilled water, and the second results from the dissolution of 4.8 g of ammonium molybdate in 250 mL of distilled water. After mixing the two solutions in a 1 L volumetric flask, 55 mL of concentrated H_2SO_4 are carefully added, and the resultant solution is diluted with distilled water to the mark.
- B3: Solution of p-Nitrophenol (0.25 %). Weigh 0.25 g of p-Nitrophenol in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with ethanol.
- B4: Solution of NH_3 (5%). Add 20 mL of NH_3 in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.
- B5: Solution of H_2SO_4 (5%). Add 5.1 mL of H_2SO_4 in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.
- B6: This solution must be prepared just before the measurement process and is made by weighing 1 g of ascorbic acid in a 100 mL flask and diluting to the mark with solution B2.
- Preparing a phosphorus stock solution to make the standards is also necessary. To prepare this solution, it is necessary to weigh 4.3938 g of KH_2PO_4 (dried at 40 °C), dissolve it in distilled water and make it up to 1000 mL. The phosphorus concentration in this solution is 1000 mg L^{-1} .

The procedure is the following:

- First, 1 g of sieved dry soil (m) is weighted in a Greiner tube and 10 mL of solution B1 is added (VE).
 - This suspension is shaken for 30 min and filtered by 0.45 μm .
 - In a 50 mL volumetric flask, an aliquot of the filtered suspension is added (0.1-0.5 mL). The volume used depends on the expected amount of phosphorus (VS).
-

The following solutions are added to the flask

- 0.5 mL of boric acid.
- 2-3 drops of B3 solution.
- 2-3 drops of B4 solution (until the solution turns yellow).
- 2-3 drops of B5 solution (until the solution becomes colourless).
- 5 mL of B6 solution.
- Dilute to the mark with water.

It is necessary to employ the same procedure with the blank and the standards that will be used in the calibration, replacing the soil with a known concentration of phosphorus. Patterns of 0,04, 0.08, 0.12, 0.16 and 0.24 mg L⁻¹ are usually employed.

Calculations

To present the results, the phosphorus content is usually referenced to grams of dry soil. For this, we can use the following formula:

$$C_p = (A - B) \frac{V_E}{V_S} \frac{50}{m}$$

Where:

CP is the extractable phosphorus content in the soil (in mg of P g⁻¹ of dry soil)

A is the P concentration in the sample (mg mL⁻¹)

B is the P concentration in the blank (mg mL⁻¹)

VE is the volume of extractant used (mL).

VS is the volume of sample measured by colourimetry (mL).

m is the soil mass (g)

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4.6 Effective cation exchange capacity and sum of bases

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Principle & Application

Cation exchange capacity (CEC) represents the total number of negative bonds of the colloidal soil complex, expressed in cmol per kg of soil.

CEC is an index of soil fertility since it provides information about the content of nutrients that a soil can retain by ionic exchange and the nutrients available for the plants. CEC values of 8-10 cmol kg⁻¹ are usually considered the minimum acceptable for an Ap horizon in cultivated soils to obtain a satisfactory production (Porta et al. 1999).

The method to determine the CEC shown here is the determination of the effective cation exchange capacity and base saturation level using barium chloride solution as exchangeable salt (ISO 2018).

Equipment & Material

- Shaker, rotary shaker (end-over-end) or horizontal
- Tightly locking polyethylene centrifuge tubes (ca. 50 mL)
- 50 or 100 mL polyethylene (PE) flasks
- Funnels
- Filter paper (Whatman No. 42, Schleicher & Schuell 595 1/2, Macherey-Nagel 261 G 1/4, or similar)
- Glass vacuum line (e.g. electric pump)
- Flame atomic absorption spectrometer (FAAS) or ICP-OES

Reagents

- Deionised water (electric conductivity $< 0.2 \text{ mS m}^{-1}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)
- Barium chloride (BaCl_2) solution; $c(\text{BaCl}_2) = 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dissolve 24.43 g of $\text{BaCl}_2 \times 2 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ in 1000 mL of water (use volumetric flask)
- BaCl_2 solution; $c(\text{BaCl}_2) = 0.0025 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dilute 25 mL of solution BaCl_2 solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) in 1000 mL of water
- Magnesium sulphate solution; $c(\text{MgSO}_4) = 0.020 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dissolve 4.930 g magnesium sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$) in 1000 mL of water (use volumetric flask). Prepare fresh solution. Magnesium sulphate can lose crystal water during storage. Protect from that by wrapping the flask in an additional PE bag and storing the chemical in a refrigerator
- Hydrochloric acid, $c(\text{HCl}) = 12 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ ($\rho = 1.19 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$)

Reagents

- Magnesium standard solution; $c(\text{Mg}) = 0.0010 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Add 50 mL of MgSO_4 solution (0.020 mol L^{-1}) to a 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up with water to the mark (see Remarks).
- Acidified lanthanum solution: $c(\text{La}) = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Add 15.6 mg lanthanum nitrate hexahydrate [$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \times 6 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$] to a 500 mL volumetric flask, add 42 mL hydrochloric acid (12 mol L^{-1}), and fill up with water to 500 mL
- Acidified caesium chloride solution: Dissolve 10 g caesium chloride in some water. Add 83 mL of hydrochloric acid (12 mol L^{-1}), and make up to 1000 mL with water
- Sodium and potassium stock solution: $c(\text{Na}) = 400 \text{ mg/L}$, $c(\text{K}) = 1000 \text{ mg/L}$. Dissolve 1.0168 g sodium chloride and 1.9068 g potassium chloride in water. Transfer to 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up to the mark with water (see Remarks)
- Diluted stock solution: $c(\text{Na}) = 40 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Pipette 25 mL of solution ($c(\text{Na}) = 400 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 1000 \text{ mg/L}$) in 250 mL volumetric flask and fill up with water to the mark (see Remarks).
- Hydrochloric acid, $c(\text{HCl}) = 4 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Add 83 mL of concentrated HCl ($\rho = 1.19 \text{ g/cm}^3$) to water, to receive a total volume of 1000 mL
- Calcium stock solution: $c(\text{Ca}) = 1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Dissolve 2.497 g calcium carbonate in water. Transfer to 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up to the mark with water (see Remarks).
- Magnesium stock solution: $c(\text{Mg}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Dissolve 1.0168 g sodium chloride and 0.836 g magnesium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2 \times 6 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$) in water. Transfer to 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up to the mark with water (see Remarks)

PROCEDURE

Leaching and measurement of soil bases:

- Weigh 2.50 g of air-dried soil into a polyethylene centrifuge tube of about 50 mL capacity. Close cap tightly. Note the combined mass of tube and soil (m_1).
- Add 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and shake for 1 h. Subsequently centrifuge the tubes at 3,000 g for 10 min. Note: Balance tubes before centrifugation. Transfer the supernatant liquid to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Repeat this procedure, i.e. the addition of 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution, shaking and centrifugation twice more. Collect all three supernatants in the same volumetric flask. Make up to the volume of the volumetric flask with BaCl_2 (0.1 mol L^{-1}). Mix, filter and store the extract I for the determination of the exchangeable concentration of Na, K, Ca and Mg (sum of bases).
- Calibration for Na, K, Ca and Mg determination: Prepare solutions with 0 mL, 5 mL, 10 mL, 15 mL, 20 mL and 25 mL of the diluted stock solution ($c(\text{Na}) = 40 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in 50 mL volumetric flasks. Add 10.0 mL of extraction solution BaCl_2 (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and 5.0 mL of acidified caesium chloride solution. Fill up to the mark with water. The resulting concentrations of Na are 0, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 mg L^{-1} . The resulting concentrations of K are 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 mg L^{-1} . Prepare solutions with 0 mL, 2 mL, 4 mL, 6 mL, 8 mL and 10 mL of the stock solution ($c(\text{Ca}) 1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{Mg}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in 100 mL volumetric flasks. The resulting concentrations of Ca are 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 mg L^{-1} . The resulting concentrations of Mg are 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 mg L^{-1} .

- Analysis: Fill 2.0 mL of the extract I and of the blank sample, respectively, into reaction tubes. Add 1.0 mL of acidified caesium chloride solution and 7.0 mL of water and mix (See Remarks). Determine bases with FAAS or ICP-EOS, with the instrument set according to the manufacturer's instructions for optimum performance.

PROCEDURE

Cleansing & Re-exchange

Cleansing:

- Add 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution ($0.0025 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) to the soil pellet and shake overnight. (Resulting Ba concentration in the equilibrium solution will be about 0.01 mol L^{-1}). Centrifuge tubes at 3,000 g for 10 min. Decant the supernatant liquid.

Re-exchange:

- Weigh the tube with its contents and cap (m_2). Add 30 mL of MgSO_4 solution (0.020 mol L^{-1}) to the soil pellet and shake overnight. Centrifuge tubes at 3,000 g for 10 min. Decant the supernatant through a filter paper into a new flask and store the extract II for the determination of the concentration of excess Mg.
- Prepare blank samples without the addition of soil in parallel and follow the above described procedure completely.

PROCEDURE

Determination of CEC

- Pipette 0.20 mL from the extracts II of the samples and blank samples into 100 mL volumetric flasks.
 - Add 0.3 mL of the BaCl₂ solution (0.1 mol L⁻¹) and additional 10 mL of acidified lanthanum solution (10 mg L⁻¹).
 - Fill up with water to the mark and mix.
 - For calibration, use dilutions of the Mg standard solution (10 mg L⁻¹). Pipette 0 mL, 1 mL, 2 mL, 3 mL, 4 mL, and 5 mL into a series of 100 mL volumetric flasks. Add 10 mL of acidified lanthanum solution (10 mg L⁻¹) to each flask and fill up to the mark with water. Final concentration of the calibration solutions: 0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 mmol L⁻¹, respectively.
 - Analyse Mg using FAAS at a wavelength of 285.2 nm or using ICP-OES with instrumentation settings following the manufacturer's instructions for optimum performance of the instrument.
-

Calculations

Correct the concentrations of Mg in the sample solutions for the volume of the liquid retained by the centrifuged soil after being treated with 0,0025 mol L⁻¹ BaCl₂ solution:

$$c_2 = [c_1 (30 + m_2 - m_1)] / 30$$

where:

c₂ is the corrected Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L⁻¹]

c₁ is the Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L⁻¹]

m₁ is the mass of the centrifuge tube with air-dried soil [g]

m₂ is the mass of the centrifuge tube with wet soil [g]

Calculate the cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the soil using the following equation:

$$CEC = (c_{b1} - c_2) 3,000 / m$$

where:

CEC is the cation exchange capacity of the soil [cmolc kg⁻¹]

c₂ is the corrected Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L⁻¹]

c_{b1} is the Mg concentration in the blank [mmol L⁻¹]

m is the mass of the air-dried sample [g]

If the CEC exceeds 40 cmolc kg⁻¹, the determination should be repeated using less soil, adjusting the calculation accordingly

Calculations

Calculate the soil bases as follows:

$$c(\text{Na, exchangeable}) = 2.1749 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{\text{blank}}) / m \text{ [cmolc kg}^{-1}\text{]}$$

$$c(\text{K, exchangeable}) = 1.2788 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{\text{blank}}) / m \text{ [cmolc kg}^{-1}\text{]}$$

$$c(\text{Ca, exchangeable}) = 8.2288 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{\text{blank}}) / m \text{ [cmolc kg}^{-1}\text{]}$$

$$c(\text{Mg, exchangeable}) = 4.9903 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{\text{blank}}) / m \text{ [cmolc kg}^{-1}\text{]}$$

with the measured concentrations in the diluted sample (c_{sample}) and the diluted blank sample (c_{blank}), respectively, and m is the soil mass in g.

Remarks

If the barium chloride extract has a yellowish-brown colour, this indicates that some organic matter has been dissolved. If this occurs, record it in the test report.

As an alternative to the preparation of standards and calibration series, respectively, certified standard solutions are commercially available; aliquots are diluted as required.

For a complete analysis of exchangeable cations, it might be reasonable to additionally determine NH_4^+ in fertilised agricultural soil and exchangeable Al in acidic and also Fe in very acidic soil.

Any other volumes can be used as well, as long as the same concentrations are obtained and the final sample volume is sufficient for analysis with FAAS or ICP-OES.

Dilutions can be prepared much faster doing pipette dilutions and using a diluter system, respectively.

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4.7 Oxalate extractable Al and Fe

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Principle & Application

Oxalate has been frequently used to quantify poorly crystalline pedogenic aluminium (Al) and iron (Fe).

In the dark, acid oxalate (pH 3) differentiates amorphous Fe oxides from more crystalline Fe oxides (Schwertmann, 1964). OH groups of an oxide's surface are protonated at low pH, weakening Fe-O bonds.

So, Fe is complexed by the oxalate and the Fe oxide is dissolved (Cornell and Schwertmann, 2003).

Equipment & Material

- Precision balance
- Falcon tubes or 15 mL screw-cap plastic centrifuge tube
- Magnetic stirrer
- Shaker
- Centrifuge
- pH meter
- ICP-OES or atomic absorption
- Reagents
- Solution A: Ammonium oxalate solution $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ H_2O , 0.2 M (28.3 g L^{-1}).
- Solution B: Oxalic acid solution $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.2 M (25.2 g L^{-1}).
- Mix 700 mL of A and 535 mL of B, check pH, and adjust to 3.0 by adding A or B.
- Certified atomic absorption standards, 1%.
- Deionized water

PROCEDURE

Weigh 0.250 g of <2 mm air-dry soil, ground to pass a 0.15 mm (100 mesh) sieve, into a 15 mL screw-cap plastic centrifuge tube (weigh 0.125 g for samples with >2% extractable Fe or Al).

Add 10 mL of the acid ammonium oxalate solution and stopper the tube tightly.

Place the tubes in an end-over-end shaker and shake for 4 h in the dark. A horizontal shaker can also be used, although interparticle abrasion can be increased.

Centrifuge the tubes for 20 min at 510 g (centrifuge at higher speed for samples rich in clay particles), decant the clear supernatant into a suitable container, and analyze it within a few days. Extracts should be stored in the dark to avoid the photoinduced degradation of oxalate and the subsequent precipitation of dissolved metals.

To determine Al and Fe by atomic absorption:

$$\% \text{ Fe, Al} = \frac{\text{mg mL}^{-1} - \text{in final solution} \times \text{extractant (mL)} \times \text{dilution}}{\text{sample weight (g)} \times 10,000}$$

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4.8 Available metals and metalloids (As, Cd, Mo, Co, Cu, Cr, Mn, Zn, Hg, Ni, Pb, Sb and V)

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Principle & Application

Metals in soil can be found in different forms: as free ions or forming complexed in the soil solution, adsorbed or as exchangeable form in the colloidal fraction of soil (clay, humic compounds, hydroxides of iron, manganese and aluminium) or as part of secondary, primary and complex minerals insoluble in the solid phase of the soil (Kiekens, 1995; Viets, 1962).

The exchangeable fraction of metals includes metals that are weakly adsorbed on solid soil surfaces (clays, Fe and Mn oxides, organic matter) (Kiekens, 1995; Viets, 1962) and which are retained by a relatively weak electrostatic interaction. These metals can be released by a process of ion exchange. Exchangeable metal ions are a measure of those metals that are most easily released into the soil solution (González-Flores et al., 2011).

The present method is based on extracting heavy metals from soil with an unbuffered 0.01 M CaCl_2 solution. This method is used to estimate soil contamination and the availability of metals to plants. This has been recommended in European countries to assess soil fertility (Houba et al., 1996). It combines an adequate extraction capacity with a low salt concentration in the extract salt concentration, which facilitates the determination of metals because the matrix where they are found is less complex (Pueyo et al., 2004).

Equipment & Material

- Beakers (1000 mL)
- Falcon tubes with skirts (50 mL)
- Glass funnels (5 cm)
- Plastic vials (50 mL)
- Test tubes (10 mL)
- Test tubes (50 mL)
- Quantitative filter paper with 90 mm of diameter (7-11 mm pore diameter)
- Precision balance
- Centrifuge
- Stirring plate
- Magnetic stirrer
- Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS)
- Reagents
- Milli-Q water (Type I)
- CaCl_2 (0.01 M): weigh 1.4702 g of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1000 mL beaker, shake and make up to 1L with Milli-Q water in a volumetric flask.

Procedure

Preparation of the extract

- To weigh 4 g of sieved soil (< 2 mm) using a precision balance in a falcon tube (50 mL) and note the exact weight.
- To add 40 mL of 0.01 M CaCl₂ to the falcon tube containing the soil sample.
- To shake for 2 h on the stirring plate.
- To centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 5 min.
- To filter the extract through filter paper using a funnel.
- To store the extract in a 50 mL vial. If the extract remains cloudy, filter through a 0.45 µm filter.
- To transfer the extract contained in the vials to 10 mL tubes to facilitate measurements in ICP-MS.
- To label the sample appropriately and refrigerate. The solution can be stored for 1 month, if a longer time is foreseen, it is necessary to add HNO₃ (65%) to the solution.
- To measure through ICP-MS.

Calculations

Convert the extract concentration obtained from the instrument in mg/L to mg/kg dry-weight of sample by:

$$\text{Metals or metalloid (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{M V}{W} \text{ DF}$$

Where,

X is the concentration obtained from the instrument [mg L⁻¹],

V is the final volume of the sample solution [mL],

W is the weight of the sample [g],

DF is the dilution factor (DF = 1.00 with no sample dilution).

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4.9 Total metals and metalloids (As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Sb, V and Zn)

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Principle & Application

All plants require 17 elements to complete their life cycle, and an additional four elements have been identified as essential for some plants (Havlin et al., 2005).

Except for C, H, and O, which plants obtain from air and water, plants derive the remaining 14 elements from the soil or through fertilisers, manures, and amendments (Parikh & James, 2012). The bulk of the soil solid fraction is constituted by soil minerals, which exert significant direct and indirect influences on the supply and availability of most nutrient elements.

Soil parent material has a significant direct influence on the nutrient element contents of the soil and their concentrations depending on rock type. Therefore, it is helpful to determine their total concentrations to understand the dynamic of nutrients in soil better.

In addition, soils may become contaminated by the accumulation of heavy metals and metalloids through anthropogenic activities. The adequate protection and restoration of soil agro-ecosystems contaminated by heavy metals requires a detailed soil characterisation, with total metals concentrations being an essential parameter.

A representative sample is extracted and/or dissolved in concentrated nitric acid, or alternatively, concentrated nitric acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid, using microwave heating with a suitable laboratory microwave unit. The sample and acid(s) are placed in a microwave vessel. The vessel is sealed and heated in the microwave unit for a specified period of time. After cooling, the vessel contents are filtered, centrifuged, or allowed to settle and then diluted to volume and analysed using the appropriate determinative method (USEPA, 1997).

Equipment & Material

- Volumetric flask (100 mL)
- Funnels
- Quantitative filter papers of 110 mm diameter (0.45 μm pore size)
- Pipette (10 mL)
- Microwave unit
- Vessels
- Analytical balance
- Flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (FLAA) or graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GFAA) or inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer (ICP-AES) or inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS)

Reagents

- Concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) 65%
- Concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) 37%
- Deionised water

Procedure

- Weigh 0.500 g of well-mixed ground soil sample into a microwave vessel to the nearest 0.001 g with an appropriate analytical balance.
- Add 10 mL of concentrated nitric acid or, alternatively, 9 mL of concentrated nitric acid and 3 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid to the vessel in a fume hood. The addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid to the nitric acid is appropriate for stabilising high Fe and Al concentrations in the solution.
- Seal the vessel according to the manufacturer's instructions. Properly place the vessel in the microwave system according to the manufacturer's recommended specifications and, when applicable, connect appropriate temperature and pressure sensors to vessels according to the manufacturer's specifications.
- Start the microwave program. The temperature of each sample should rise to $175 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ in approximately 5.5 ± 0.25 min and remain at $175 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ for 4.5 min, and stay for at least 10-min reducing the temperature (Fig. 1).
- At the end of the microwave program, allow the vessels to cool for a minimum of 30 min before removing them from the microwave system. Internal or external cooling devices may accelerate cooling of the vessels.

- Complete the sample preparation by venting microwave containers in a fume hood before uncapping, to avoid a rush of acid vapour that may still be in the headspace. When cool enough to handle, carefully uncap the vessels.
- Filter the sample solution through quantitative filter paper into a 100 mL volumetric flask, and make up to 100 mL with deionised water.
- The solution is now ready for analysis for elements of interest using appropriate elemental analysis techniques (Flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (FLAA) or graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GFAA) or inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer (ICP-AES) or inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS).

Figure: Temperature and pressure profile (Link et al., 1997, 1998)

Calculations

Convert the extract concentration obtained from the instrument in mg/L to mg/kg dry-weight of sample by:

$$\text{Sample concentration (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{X V}{W} \text{ DF}$$

Where,

X is the concentration obtained from the instrument [mg L⁻¹],

V is the final volume of the sample solution [mL] (e.g. volumetric flask of 100 mL),

W is the weight of the sample [g],

DF is the dilution factor (DF = 1.00 with no sample dilution)

Remarks

All digestion vessels must be carefully acid washed and rinsed with reagent water. When switching between high concentration samples and low concentration samples, all digestion vessels should be cleaned by leaching with hot (1:1) hydrochloric acid (greater than 80°C, but less than boiling) for a minimum of two hours followed by hot (1:1) nitric acid (greater than 80°C, but less than boiling) for a minimum of two hours. The vessels should then be rinsed with deionised water and dried in a clean environment.

The addition of hydrochloric acid may limit the quantitation techniques and increase the difficulties of analysis for some quantitation systems.

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4.10 Available B

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Principle & Application

ABoron is one of the 16 essential nutrients for plants and needs to be available according to the growth needs of the crop (Motsara and Roy, 2008).

Its presence in the soil depends to a large extent on the texture, pH and irrigation: the deficiency of this element is usually caused by irrigation or heavy rain in acid soils with a light texture. Comparing the data for all essential micronutrients, boron is one of the most studied since it is the one that causes deficiencies more frequently (Keren and Bingham, 1958).

The lack of this element affects crops, such as shortening the internodes or stopping terminal growth. Symptoms of a boron deficiency in crops may take time to appear, as in the case of phosphorus deficiency.

When determining available boron, there are various extractants (Table x), but water extraction is usually used (Berger and Truog, 1939): soil boron that can be dissolved in water is considered available boron. It is generally measured by atomic emission spectrometry or by a colorimetric method using a reagent such as Azometin-H.

Method	Reference
Hot Water	Bergar and Truog (1939)
CaCl ₂	Aitken et al (1987)
NH ₄ oxalate (pH 3.75)	De Endredy (1963)
NH ₄ /DTPA	Handreck (1990)

Table: Methods employed to extract boron from a soil (Adapted from Nable et al., 1997)

Equipment & materials

- Falon tubes (50 mL)
- Water-bath with magnetic stirrer
- Centrifuge
- Balance
- Spoon
- Desionized water
- Micro filters
- Syringe
- ICP-MS

Procedure

- To weight 5 g of sieved soil (< 2 mm) in Falcon tubes
- To add 25 mL of desionized water
- To shake the samples in the water-bath for 90 minutes at 50°C
- To centrifuge at 2500 rpm for 5 minutes
- To filter the samples with micro filters
- To measure the extract by ICP-MS

Calculations

The boron concentration obtained by ICP-MS is in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and it is necessary to convert it to mg of B per kg of dry soil. Since we added 25 mL of water to the soil to extract the boron:

$$B (\text{mg kg}^{-1}) = \frac{M \times V \times Df}{W}$$

Where,

M is the boron concentration measured through ICP-MS in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$

V is the total volume of the extract in mL

Df is the dilution factor. If the sample has not been diluted, this factor is not applicable

W is the dry weight of the sample

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4.11 Available S (sulfate)

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Principle & Application

Sulfur is an essential macronutrient for plants, particularly for synthesizing the amino acids such as cysteine, cystine and methionine in tree tissues, as well as essential vitamins and cofactors.

Plants absorb S mainly as sulfate, although organic S forms (S bonded to ester S or carbon) are important S sources to the plants. S cycling within the soil is mainly based on the mineralization of organic S forms to inorganic sulfate and the reverse process, namely the immobilization of sulfate due to its incorporation into soil organic compounds, both processes mediated by soil microorganisms (Kertesz and Mirleau, 2004).

Available S (sulfate) extraction in soil samples is carried out with a solution of sodium phosphate (NaH_2PO_4), and subsequent measure using ion chromatography ([Tanikawa et al., 1999](#)).

The soil used for this determination of inorganic nitrogen has to be kept at 4°C at field-moist conditions since the air-drying of soils increases the amount of extractable sulfate. The sample is stored at 4°C if analyzed within 3 days from sampling. Otherwise, it is stored at -20°C to avoid the loss of sulfate.

Equipment & materials

- Precision balance.
- Plastic vials (50 mL).
- Volumetric flask (100 mL).
- Rotating plate.
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL).
- Centrifuge.
- Syringe filters (0.2 μm).
- Syringe (10 mL).
- Ion chromatography equipment.

Reagents

Solution of potassium chloride (2 M KCl): dissolve 149 g of potassium chloride (KCl) in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H_2O . Fill up to the final volume with deionised water.

Stock or commercial sulfate solution (1000 mg L^{-1} SO_4^{2-}).

Procedure

- Homogenize the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred in a refrigerator container.
- Weigh 2.5 g of sieved field-moist soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of solution of potassium chloride (2 M KCl): (soil / extractant ratio 1:10).
- Shake for 60 min on the rotating plate.
- Centrifuge the samples for 2 min at 5000 rpm. Filter supernatant using syringe filters.
- The extract obtained is measured in the ion chromatography equipment.
- Prepare a calibration curve from the SO₄²⁻ stock solution.

Calculations

$$\text{SO}_4^{2-} (\text{mg kg}^{-1}) = \frac{(C \times V \times df)}{m}$$

C is the concentration of sulfate obtained from ion chromatography (mg L⁻¹)

V is the total volume of the added NaH₂PO₄ solution (25 mL)

df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1

m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture)

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4.12 Total Pesticides

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Principle & Application

Currently, 479 active substances can be used as pesticides at the European level, and the other 43 are pending approval (European Commission 2009). These pesticides are used to protect plants against possible pests and have contributed to increasing production during the last decades (Silva et al. 2019).

However, pesticides can reach the ground during the application or by rain (Pérez-Rodríguez et al. 2017), and, given their effects on living organisms, they have become a major threat to the soil, biodiversity, and food security (Stolte, Tesfai, and Keizer 2016).

Therefore, when examining the biodiversity of soil, it is also essential to determine the pesticides present.

To measure pesticides, we use the QUECHERS method (Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, and Safe), based on a European Standard (EN 15662:2018) for the determination of pesticide residues on foods of plant origin, and adapted to measure soil samples (Mol et al. 2008; Silva et al. 2019).

This method is based on pesticide extraction with one or several solvents, the cleaning of the sample to avoid interferences and the determination of pesticides by LC-MS/MS and GC-HRMS.

Equipment & materials

- Analytical balance.
- Weighing funnel, glass
- Micropipettes.
- Spatula
- Pasteur pipettes
- Syringe (10 μ L)
- Greiner tubes of 50 mL.
- Falcon tubes of 15 and 50 mL
- Bottle dispenser of 10 mL
- Topaz flasks of 10 and 60 mL
- LC vials.
- Spherical flasks of 50 mL

Equipment & materials

- Shaker.
- Distilled water and Milli-Q water.
- Vortex.
- Centrifuge.
- Air compressor
- Nitrogen generator
- Vertical Multi-function Rotator
- Nylon filter membranes, pore size 0.20 μm
- Eppendorf vials.
- GC vials.
- Capillary column 2 x 15 m x 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μm . HP-5MS (or similar)
- Column C18 (100 mm x 2.1 mm internal diameter x 1.7 μm particle size)
- Liquid Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer (LC-MS/MS).
- High-Resolution Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer (GC-HRMS).

All volumetric gauging equipment shall be of class A according to the applicable ISO standards.

Reagents

- Helium. Grade 5.0 or higher
- Argon. Grade 5.0 or higher
- Industrial nitrogen
- Industrial air
- Extra pure nitrogen
- Magnesium sulphate (MgSO_4 ; $\geq 99.8\%$).
- Ammonium formate (CH_5NO_2 $\geq 97\%$)
- Methanol for HPLC (CH_3OH , $\geq 99.9\%$)
- Formic acid (CH_2O_2 , $\geq 98\%$)
- Acetic acid (CH_3COOH ; $\geq 99.8\%$) (HAc).
- Sodium acetate (CH_3COONa ; 99%).
- Acetonitrile ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{N}$; 99.95% LC grade) (ACN).
- Mili-Q water
- Water HPLC grade

Reagents

- Analytical standards. High grade
- QUECHERS salts
- Anhydrous magnesium sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \geq 99.8\%$)
- Sodium chloride (NaCl)
- Trisodium citrate dihydrate ($\text{Na}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (reagent grade)
- Disodium hydrogen citrate sesquihydrate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{Na}_2\text{O}_8$) (reagent grade)

Procedure - Extraction

- Weigh 10 g of the soil sample
- Add 10mL of Millipore Water and 10mL ACN within a 50 mL Greiner tube.
- The tube with this mixture was agitated (end-over-end) for 10 min.

Procedure - Cleaning the solution

- Add QuEChERS salts (4 g of MgSO₄, 1g of NaCl, 1 g of trisodium citrate dehydrate, and 0.5 g of disodium hydrogen citrate sesquihydrate)
- Stir by vortex (10 min) and centrifuge for 10 min at 3500 rpm.
- Collect supernatant and transfer to Eppendorf tubes for UPLC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS analyses.

The supernatant is analysed by two methods: LC-MS / MS and GC-HRMS.

Procedure - For LC-MS / MS

- Add 100 μ L of the supernatant and 900 μ L of formic water 0.01%: MeOH (80:20; v/v) were added directly into a LC vial to be analysed.
- Measure using LC-MS / MS.

Procedure - For GC-HRMS there is an extra cleaning step

- 1000 μL of the supernatant were evaporated and recomposed with 1000 μL of internal standard.
- Measure using GC-HRMS .

The determinations through GC-MS/MS were carried out on an Agilent 7000 Triple Quad GC/MS, while ULC-MS/MS were carried out on Agilent 1290. The determinations in UPLC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS were made in duplicate. As for the calibrations, they were carried out with multi-pesticide standards that also included the internal standard. The standards were measured each 25 samples. The LC-MS/MS and GC-HRMS apparatus and conditions are described in Tables 3.11.1 and 3.11.2, respectively.

Chemical Analyses

Type of LC	UPLC-MS/MS Agilent 1290 Infinity coupled to Agilent 1290 infinity Column Oven and Exion LC system.			
Hot Water	AB SCIEX TQ 5500			
Scan time	0.4 min			
ESI	Positive and Negative			
Column	Column C18 (100 mm x 2.1 mm internal diameter x 1.7 μ m)			
LC gradient	min	Flow rate (mL/min)	A(%)	B (%)
Hot Water	0	0.35	95	5
	1	0.35	70	30
	2.3	0.35	50	50
	5	0.35	30	70
	9.3	0.35	20	80
	10	0.35	10	90
	11	0.35	0	100
	13	0.35	0	100
	13.5	0.35	95	5
	15	0.35	95	5
Flow rate	0.35 l min ⁻¹			
Mass spectrometer conditions:	Temperature source 450oC Curtain gas 30 Ion Spray volt +4500; -4500.			

Table 3.11.1. Experimental conditions for LC-MS/MS apparatus.

Type of GC	Agilent 7000 Triple Quad GC/MS
Ion Polarity	Positive
Column	Capillary column #1: AGILENT HP-5 15 m x 250 μ m x 0.25 μ m Capillary column #2: AGILENT HP-5 15 m x 250 μ m id. x 0.25 μ m thickness
Column temperature	70oC
Oven temperature program	60oC
Carrier gas	Helium 5.0 (99.999%)
Inyection mode	Splittles
Mass spectrometer conditions	Working temperatures Source: 250 °C Trasnfer line: 250°C Ionisation mode: electronic ionisation at -70 eV.
Injection volume	1 μ l

Table 3.11.2. Experimental conditions for GC-HRMS apparatus.

The pesticides measured are summarized in Table 3.11.3., taken from the work of Silva et al. (2019).

Compound	Type	Chemical class
Abamectin	Insecticide	Botanical
Aldrin	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Atrazine	Herbicide	Triazine
Atrazine-deisopropyl	Metabolite of simazine and atrazine	Unclassified
Atrazine-desethyl	Metabolite of atrazine	Triazine
Azoxystrobin	Fungicide	Strobilurin
Boscalid	Fungicide	Carboxamide
Carbaryl	Insecticide	Carbamate
Carbofuran	Insecticide; metabolite of furathiocarb, carbosulfan and benfuracarb	Carbamate
Carbofuran,3-hydroxy	Metabolite of carbofuran, carbosulfan and benfuracarb	Unclassified
Carbofuran, -keto	Metabolite of carbofuran and benfuracarb	Unclassified
Chlordane alpha	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Chlordane gamma	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Chlordecone	Insecticide; metabolite of mirex and kelevan	Organochlorine
Chlorfenvinphos	Insecticide	Organophosphate

Table 3.11.3. Summary of the compounds measured in the soil samples. The table also includes the type of pesticide and the chemical class.

Compound	Type	Chemical class
Chlorpyrifos	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Cymoxanil	Fungicide	Cyanoacetamide oxime
Cyproconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Cyprodinil	Fungicide	Anilinopyrimidine
DDD op	Insecticide; metabolite of DDT	Organochlorine
DDD pp	Insecticide; metabolite of DDT Metabolite of DDT	Organochlorine Organochlorine
DDE op	Insecticide; metabolite of DDT Metabolite of DDT	Organochlorine Organochlorine
DDE pp	Metabolite of DDT Insecticide	Organochlorine Organochlorine
DDT op	Metabolite of DDT Insecticide	Organochlorine Organochlorine
DDT pp	Metabolite of carbofuran and benfuracarb	Organochlorine
Diazinon	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Dieldrin	Insecticide, metabolite of aldrin	Organochlorine
Chlordecone	Insecticide; metabolite of mirex and kelevan	Organophosphate
Chlorfenvinphos	Insecticide	Organophosphate

Table 3.11.3. Summary of the compounds measured in the soil samples. The table also includes the type of pesticide and the chemical class.

Compound	Type	Chemical class
Difenoconazole	Fungicide	Morpholine
Diuron	Herbicide	Phenylamide
Endosulfan alpha	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Endosulfan beta	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Endosulfan sulphate	Metabolite endosulfan, endosulfan alpha and endosulfan beta	Unclassified
Endrin	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Epoxiconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Ethion	Insecticide, metabolite of chlormephos	Organophosphate
Fenpropimorph	Fungicide	Morpholine
Fluometuron	Herbicide	Phenylurea
Fluroxypyr	Herbicide	Pyridine compound
Folpet	Fungicide	Phthalimide
Heptachlor	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Hexachlorobenzene	Insecticide, metabolite of HCH gamma	Organochlorine
Hexachlorocyclohexane, beta	Metabolite of HCH gamma	Unclassified
Hexachlorocyclohexane, gamma	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Imazalil	Fungicide	Imidazole

Table 3.11.3. Summary of the compounds measured in the soil samples. The table also includes the type of pesticide and the chemical class.

Compound	Type	Chemical class
Imidacloprid	Insecticide	Neonicotinoid
Isoproturon	Herbicide	Herbicide
Isoproturon	herbicide	Herbicide
Malathion	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Metalaxyl	Fungicide	Phenylamide
Metamitron	Herbicide	Triazinole
Myclobutanil	Fungicide	Triazole
Parathion	Insecticide	Triazole
Parathion-methyl	Insecticide	
Penconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Pentachlorobenzene	Metabolite of quintozone	Unclassified
Phthalimide	Metabolite of folpet	Unclassified
Pinoxaden	Herbicide	Unclassified
Pirimiphos-methyl	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Prochloraz	Fungicide	Fungicide
Procymidone	Fungicide	Dicarboximide
Propiconazole	Fungicide	Triazole

Table 3.11.3. Summary of the compounds measured in the soil samples. The table also includes the type of pesticide and the chemical class.

Calculations

With the internal standards, a response factor can be calculated in order to determine the efficiency of the extraction procedure. The response factor is the concentration of the internal standard in the sample divided by the initial concentration of the standard. By using this response factor, it is possible to correct the concentration of pesticides measured.

The results obtained from the LC-MS / MS and GC-HRMS are in ng mL⁻¹ and should be converted in ng g⁻¹ of dry soil.

Remarks

Given the importance of glyphosate and AMPA, these two substances are usually extracted by using more specific methods (Bento et al. 2016), that will be explained in detail in the following section.

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05

SOIL STRUCTURE, WATER
AVAILABILITY AND SOIL
CARBON SEQUESTRATION

5.1 Bulk density

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Principle & Application

Bulk density is defined as soil mass per unit of volume. This volume is the sample volume in the field. Bulk density is interesting from the point of view of soil management since it informs about the compaction of each horizon and allows the identification of difficulties for emergency rooting and air and water circulation. Bulk density is directly related to the structure and depends on the same control factors. According to a soil volume taken in the field, knowledge of bulk density is essential to refer to the results of laboratory analyses.

Bulk density is often available for the different soil horizons due to the relative ease of its determination. However, it should be noted that the bulk density value has important limitations since it does not provide information about the size of the spaces, the connection between them, or the forces that have led to a specific structure.

These aspects are important to predict the water movement in the soil pores and the risks of degradation of aggregates. Soils with the same values of bulk densities may respond differently to external forces. To obtain information about this, specific studies on porosity must be used (Porta et al. 1999).

The so-called cylinder method is presented here (Campbell and Hensall 1991). A cylinder with thin, rigid walls, with a beveled edge towards the outside, of known volume is used. The method is to take a sample by inserting the cylinder into the horizon to be studied.

Equipment & materials

- Metal cylinder of known volume (100-500 cm³)
- Bulk Density Sampler Cup and Cap
- Hammer
- Spatula
- Precision balance
- Oven

Procedure

- Remove the cup of the ring.
- Take an undisturbed soil sample using a metal cylinder in each horizon where you want to know the bulk density.
- Remove the cylinder manually or with a spatula.
- Cover the cylinder on both sides with the cups.
- In the laboratory, the cylinder's contents are transferred to a beaker of known weight.
- Put the glass in the oven for 24 hours at 105°C.
- Weigh the beaker and dry soil on the precision balance (this measure corresponds to the true bulk density), noting the exact weight.

Calculations

$$\rho_b = (m_2 - m_1) / V$$

- ρ_b is the bulk density of the soil [g m^{-3}]
- m_1 is the weight of the metal ring [g]
- m_2 is the weight of the metal ring + soil after drying [g]
- V is the volume of the metal ring [cm^3]

Remarks

In the case of soils with gravels and boulders (Regosols, Leptosols, Technosols) coarse constituents hinder sampling and increase measurement error.

In the case of soils with swelling clay minerals correction calculation is needed related to the field volume/dry volume ratio.

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5.2. Coarse fragments determination

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Principle & Application

Particle size analysis of soils containing coarse fragments (particles > 2 mm) requires sufficient amounts of soil material. Coarse fragments from soil have the same effect as other mulching materials in protecting the soil against the impact of raindrops (Poesen et al. 1990).

This method is based on the determination of the percentage of rock fragments and gravels in a soil through sieving (Taubner et al. 2009)

Equipment & Material

Material and equipment necessary

- Sieve (< 2 mm)
- Precision balance

Procedure

- Weight the whole soil sample (record precise weight). Sample has to be previously air-dried.
- Sieve the sample at < 2 mm.
- Weight the sieve non-passing fraction (record precise weight).

Calculations

Calculate the percentage of coarse fragments by dividing the weight retained on sieve by the original sample mass.

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5.3. Particle size distribution and texture

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Principle & Application

The particle size distribution (PSD) of soil is a characteristic that determines the soil dry bulk density, the amount of water and nutrients that the soil can retain and make available for plants and organisms, and, is also a property that conditions, in some way, its structure (Sangeeta Mukhopadhyay and Maiti 2018). This PSD is also known as texture. The PSD (or texture) is one of the features most scientists use to describe the soil and is measured for mineral particles smaller than 2 mm.

The PSD of soil is defined as the relative amount of clay (<0.002 mm), silt (0.05-0.002 mm) and sand (2-0.05 mm) presented by that soil (S. Mukhopadhyay et al. 2019).

Figure 5.3.1. USDA textural classification triangle (Adapted from Groenendyk et al. 2015)

The classification system based on the PSD shown in Figure 5.3.1 (the texture triangle of the USDA) is one of the most used. The percentage of material belonging to each group (sands, silts and clays) is represented on each side of the triangle. The texture is determined by the intersection between the three lines that cut the sides of the triangle at the point corresponding to the value of each element represented. Thus, a soil with more than 85% sand will be a sandy or loamy-sand soil, a soil that will allow a rapid flow of water but will hardly be able to store it. As the amount of clays and silts increases, the flow through the soil is reduced, improving the uptake of moisture by plants.

There are several methods for determining the distribution of particle sizes, but the idea is always to separate the different fractions (by size) and determine their quantity in each fraction. This can be achieved by sieving, sedimentation of a soil suspension, differences in the density of a suspension, and, currently, it can be achieved by laser diffraction methods (Taubner, Roth, and Tippkötter 2009). One of the most used methods for the PSD determination is the pipette method: the largest fractions (sands) are separated by sieving, using sieve meshes of 0.2 mm (for coarse sand) and 0.05 mm (for fine sand); and the finest ones (silt and clays) are determined according to their sedimentation rate calculated by Stokes law (Carter and Gregorich 2008).

Equipment & Material

- Shaker
- Oven

Reagents

- Sodium polyphosphate, (NaPO_3) n: weight 50 g of sodium polyphosphate and make up
 - 1 L with deionized water. This solution should be stored in an amber bottle and has a maximum shelf life of 2 months
 - Hydrogen peroxide, H_2O_2 (30 %)
 - Desionized water
-

Procedure - Cleaning the solution

Before starting the PSD characterization, preparing a solution of sodium polyphosphate in water that will be used as a dispersant is necessary. To determine the particle size distribution, 2 g of dry soil (sieved by 2 mm) is weighed in a vial of 50 mL. After that, the organic matter is eliminated by wet combustion (by adding H_2O_2).

Once the mineral part is separated, the vial is put on the over to complete the digestion reaction (at $80^\circ C$ during 1 h). After the soil sample is dry, 0.1 g of soil is weighed in a tube of 10 mL, and 10 mL of the solution of sodium polyphosphate is added to the tube. The tube with the sample is shaken well to homogenise (2 hours) and measured using a laser diffraction device to determine the proportion of each particle size in the soil (fine sand, sand, silt and clay).

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5.4. Aggregate stability and size distribution

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Principle & Application

Individual soil particles are not randomly arranged, but they form clods and lumps joined by colloidal material, which have a certain internal organization and a characteristic external shape called aggregates. The nature and distribution of aggregate size and pore space are called soil structure and play an important role in its physical properties.

The soil structure is related to the individual soil particles' mutual arrangement, the aggregate state's stability and pore size. Aggregates stability refers to their ability to maintain their shape when they are subjected to artificially induced forces, in particular those derived from wetting or the impact of raindrops (Díaz et al. 1994).

This method analyses the aggregate stability and size distribution based on a wet sieving method of air-dried soil (Elliot 1986).

Equipment & Material

- 8 mm sieve
- Two white basins with diameter of 50 cm and height of 8 cm
- 2000 μm , 250 μm , 53 μm sieves with diameter of 30 cm
- Aluminium pans for drying soil samples
- Air-forced drying oven (60°C)
- Spatula and brush
- Rinsing bottle
- Balance (2 significant digits)

Calculations

The results are expressed as a percentage showing the proportions of the different aggregate size classes.

Procedure

- To sieve sample from air-dried soil with a 8 mm sieve.
- Take 80 g subsample from air-dried soil that went through the 8 mm sieve (weigh and record precise weight).
- Fill up the white basin with water until the water level is approximately 1 cm above 2000 μm sieve-mesh.
- Spray soil evenly out on the sieve and wait for 5 minutes.
- After the 5 minutes, sieve the soil for two minutes by moving the sieve up and down (approx. 3 cm amplitude) 50 times with a slight angle to ensure that water and small particles pass through the mesh.
- Let the sieve stand for 30 seconds to let small particles settle down.
- Aspirate off the floating litter into the first flask attached to the vacuum line.
- Take the sieve out of the water and rinse off the sides plus the bottom of the sieve with water to have all particles in suspension.
- Backwash > 2000 μm aggregates (i.e. large macroaggregates) into a pre-weighed small drying pan with sufficient water.
- Put the drying pan with the large macroaggregates into the 60°C forced air oven (overnight).

Procedure

- Pour the water and particles that went through the 2000 μm sieve remaining in the white basin onto a 250 μm sieve, which is held above the second white basin, and repeat the sieving procedure (in 2 minutes the sieve is moved up and down (approx. 3 cm amplitude) 50 times with a slight angle to ensure that water and small particles pass through the mesh).
- Take the sieve out of the water and rinse off the sides plus the bottom of the sieve with water in order to have all particles in suspension.
- Backwash 250-2000 μm aggregates (i.e. small macroaggregates) into a pre-weighed small drying pan.
- Put the drying pan with the small macroaggregates into the 60°C forced air oven (overnight).
- Pour the water and particles that went through the 250 μm sieve remaining in the white basin onto a 53 μm sieve, which is held above the second white basin, and repeat the sieving procedure (in 2 minutes move the sieve up and down (approx. 3 cm amplitude) 50 times with a slight angle to ensure that water and small particles pass through the mesh).
- Take the sieve out of the water and rinse off the sides plus the bottom of the sieve with water in order to have all particles in suspension.
- Backwash 53–250 μm aggregates (i.e. microaggregates) into a pre-weighed small drying pan.
- Put the small drying pan with microaggregates into the 105°C forced air oven (overnight).
- Pour the water + < 53 μm particles (i.e. silt + clay) remaining in the white basin into a pre-weighed large drying pan.
- Put the large drying pan with silt + clay particles into the 105°C forced air oven (overnight).
- The following day weigh all fractions.

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5.5. Water content at field capacity

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Principle & Application

Soil moisture conditions are closely linked to pore volume, pore size distribution, capillary rise capacity and the groundwater table. Water tension controls the germination time of seeds. In orchards and for horticultural crops, irrigation design is based on the prediction of the dynamics of soil moisture status.

Actual soil moisture content ($m\ m^{-1}\%$ or $V\ V^{-1}\%$), however, only provides limited information on soil-plant system hydrodynamics. The available water (AW) for plant uptake is closely associated with the soil water budget (WB) (Kirkham, 2014). This is a changeable parameter which must be investigated within the total range of water capacity.

This range covers the field capacity.

Field capacity (FC) corresponds to the upper limit of AW and represents the soil moisture content left behind after the water contained in the macropores is drained by gravity (Assouline & Or, 2014).

For the determination of FC, soil samples are dried by raising the air pressure in an extractor with a porous ceramic plate. The pores of the plate are filled with water and prevent high-pressure air from flowing through. The smaller the pore size, the higher the pressure. Soil moisture will flow around the individual soil particles through the ceramic plate and an outflow tube until equilibrium is reached (i.e. air pressure in the extractor equals water tension in the samples) (UGT, 2018).

Procedure

Determination of FC by pressure plate extractor at different pressure levels in the laboratory:

- To saturate the undisturbed soil sample with distilled water
- To place the samples on the ceramic plate of 0.1 kPa type
- To set the compressor to the adequate pressure level at 33 kPa
- To measure the soil water content (SWC) of FC when equilibrium is reached

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Material and equipment necessary
- Pressure control panel equipped with two manometers 0-2 MPa and 0-0.4 MPa
- Pressure vessel(s)
- Compressor (220 V/50 Hz); maximum pressure 2.0 MPa,
- Pressure ceramic plates, 0.1 kPa standards
- Oven
- Reagents
- Distilled water

CALCULATIONS

$$FC = \left(\frac{m1 - m2}{m2} \right) \times 100$$

FC is the field capacity [%]

m1 is the wet weight of the soil after the use of the pressure plate extractor [g]

m2 is the dry weight of the soil after drying in an oven 1 day at 60 °C [g]

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5.6. Soil moisture

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Principle & Application

Soil moisture is the amount of water contained in the soil at sampling time. It is usually expressed as a percentage. It can be expressed in volume (percentage of the volume of water included in 100 cm³ of soil) or gravimetrically (percentage of the mass of water included in 100 g of soil). The proposed method is the determination of gravimetric soil moisture, weighing a soil sample before and after drying (Porta et al. 1986).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Glass crucibles
- Precision balance
- Oven

PROCEDURE

- Weigh the crucibles using the precision balance, noting the exact weight (P_c).
- Weigh approximately 10 g of soil in each crucible using the precision balance, noting the exact weight (P_s).
- Place the crucibles with the soil in the oven at 105°C for 10 h.
- Once the time has elapsed, take out the samples and put them in a desiccator until they cool.
- Weigh the crucibles with the dry soil, noting the exact weight (P_f).

CALCULATIONS

To determine the percentage of soil moisture, the following expression is applied:

$$\text{Soil moisture (\%)} = [P_s - (P_f - P_c)] / P_s \times 100$$

- P_s = weight of wet soil + crucible
- P_f = weight of crucible + dry soil
- P_c = weight of crucible

REMARKS

Soil moisture is usually determined directly on freshly sampled soil, without sieving, to know the soil water content. Then, it is recommended to avoid weighing gravels (> 2mm).

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5.7. Soil porosity

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Principle & Application

Soil porosity or pore space in a soil consists of the portion of soil volume not occupied by solid particles, either mineral or organic. Under field conditions, air and water occupy the pore space between the mineral particles. The size of individual pores depends on the shape and size of primary particles and how tightly they are packed together.

The total volume of soil occupied by pore space is calculated using particle size and density data.

Procedure

- Weigh 25 g of sieved soil (< 2 mm) and poured into a beaker with 100 mL of deionized water.
- Record the soil-water volume to calculate the particle density. Considering that 1 mL of water is 1 cm³ of water (density is 1), the difference between the soil-water volume and 100 mL of deionized water (volume of water displaced by soil) will be the volume used for the calculation of the particle density.

Calculations

- Particle density

$$\text{Particle density} = \frac{m}{V}$$

- m is the soil sample (25 g)
- V is the volume of water displaced by soil

$$\text{Soil porosity} = \left(1 - \frac{m}{V}\right) \times 100$$

- BD is the bulk density of the soil [g m⁻³]
- PD is the particle density [g m⁻³]

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5.8. Organic Matter and Carbon Content

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Principle & Application

The organic matter of the soil is a fairly complex type of natural material that has a critical role in the filtering function of the soil and in its structural stability, in the carbon cycle, and conditions the soil fertility and the retention of nutrients (Simpson and Simpson 2012). The organic matter of the soil is composed of living plants, animals and microorganisms, as well as hummus and residues of dead plants and animals in different stages of decomposition (Hillel 2004). Hummus is an important part of the soil organic matter (between 60 and 80%), it contains a large part of the nitrogen in this medium and is usually bound to inorganic materials of the matrix, so it is degraded quite slowly.

Soil organic matter contains a large proportion of organic carbon (around 58%), and these forms of carbon constitute the so-called organic soil carbon (SOC) (Iglesias Jiménez and Pérez García 1992).

This portion of the soil's organic carbon is directly related to the quality of the environment, erosion resistance, water retention and productivity (Han et al. 2017). Organic carbon has a direct effect on plant growth and is the source of energy of many of the organisms that live in the soil (Anderson and Domsch 1985). Tillage can accelerate the loss of this type of carbon by favouring mineralization or oxidation as well as losses from leachate (Lal 2002).

In addition to this SOC, inorganic forms of carbon (SIC) also appear in the soil, usually in the form of carbonates, which have a lower interest from an agricultural perspective, but which constitute an important part of the carbon store that exists in the soil (Tan et al. 2014).

The organic matter of a soil is usually determined by the method of loss-on-ignition (LOI) or using wet oxidation (WO) (Hoogsteen et al. 2015). These methods are based on the difference in weight that exists between a soil sample with and without organic matter. The difference between the two techniques (LOI and WO) rely on the way of eliminating the organic matter. Organic matter is more sensitive to heat than the mineral materials of the soil, so controlled combustion can be carried out to eliminate organic matter without affecting the rest of the soil components.

Another option is to use an oxidizing agent such as hydrogen peroxide to remove organic components. However, both methods have certain limitations. For example, the oxidation of organic matter by WO is usually incomplete, and it is necessary to apply a correction factor that depends a lot on the type of soil used. In the case of LOI, the contained water in the clays can lead to higher organic matter values than the real ones.

To determine the amount of organic and inorganic carbon, a CHN elemental analyzer is usually employed (Duan et al. 2004). For the carbon determination, the samples are burned at high temperatures to release N₂, SO₂, O₂, NO_x, CO₂ and steam.

These gases are separated using a series of columns and temperature variations, and they are passed through a thermal conductivity detector that, with the help of a series of patterns, allows the amount of carbon in the samples to be calculated. To determine organic and inorganic carbon, this method is used twice: before removing organic matter to determine total carbon and after eliminating it to determine inorganic carbon. By difference, it is possible to obtain the amount of organic carbon.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Elemental Analyzer
- Muffle
- Porcelain crucible
- Balance
- Oven
- Spatulas
- Soil mill
- Tin capsules

Procedure - Organic matter

First, it is necessary to dry the soil to prevent errors derived from moisture loss. For this, a porcelain crucible is weighed (mC). Then, about 10 grams of 2 mm sieved soil are also weighted (two replicates are made per sample). This soil is dried in an oven at 105° C until constant weight (mDS). Once the moisture is removed, the soil is weighed to obtain the initial mass and then introduced into a muffle at 450 °C for 4 hours (LOI). When finished, the soil is reweighed (mBS). The values of organic matter are usually given as a percentage (with regard to the dry soil mass).

Procedure - Carbon

To determine the total carbon, it is necessary, first, to grind a few grams of 2 mm sieved soil. About 50 mg of the soil ground is weighed in tin capsules and introduced into the Elemental Analyzer. This process must be repeated with carbon standards of known concentrations. The proportions obtained with this method must be converted into mg of total carbon per gram of dry soil.

This process is repeated once the organic matter is removed (by LOI) to determine the amount of inorganic carbon present in the sample. The amount of organic carbon is calculated as the difference between total carbon and inorganic carbon.

Calculations

- In order to calculate the percentage of organic matter in the sample (%O.M.) the following formula is applied:

$$\%O.M. = \frac{m_{DS} - m_{BS}}{m_{DS} - m_C} \cdot 100$$

WHERE

- m_{DS} is the mass of the dry soil and the porcelain crucible.
- m_{BS} is the mass of the burnt soil and the porcelain crucible.
- m_C is the mass of the porcelain crucible.
- The total carbon content (TCC) and the inorganic soil carbon (SIC) are obtained in percentage by weight (g of C in 100 grams of dry soil), a unit that can be converted to mg of C per gram of dry soil by multiplying it by 10. The SOC is calculated by:
 - SOC = TCC – SIC

Remarks

Flat-bottom crucibles are better suited to the determination of organic matter, since, by extending the soil over a larger area, the combustion is optimized.

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5.9. Particulate organic carbon and mineral associated organic carbon fractions

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Principle & Application

The interest for knowledge of the different carbon fractions, depending on their resistance and ease of degradation, lies in their importance with respect to the characterization of the C cycle and the soil as a C sink (Forbes et al. 2006; Kuyakov et al. 2009).

Soil organic matter is partially formed by particulate organic matter (POM) or particulate organic carbon (POC). POC represents the fresh or decomposing organic material (fine root fragments and other organic debris), and it serves as a readily decomposable substrate for soil microorganisms (Mrabet et al. 2001).

It is a labile pool of soil organic matter, since it supposes a transitional stage in the transformation of plant residue to soil C storage (Haumaier and Zech 1995). Mineral associated organic carbon fraction (MOC) represents the recalcitrant fraction, since it is highly resistant to microbial decomposition mainly due to its chemical structure and association with soil minerals, and thus this fraction is linked to C storage and sequestration (Laganiere et al. 2010).

The method presented here is based on the soil physical fractionation, which is useful for distinguishing specific C pools responsive to management.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Reciprocal shaker
- 0.053-mm sieve
- Porcelain crucibles 10–15 cm diameter
- Whatman filter paper 541. Hardened Ashless. CAT No. 1541-125
- Oven
- Agate mortar
- Balance
- Wash water bottle
- C and N analyser

REAGENTS

- Deionised water
- Sodium hexametaphosphate (5 g L⁻¹): dissolve 5 g of sodium hexametaphosphate in deionised water, complete to 1 L and shake well.

Procedure

- Air-dry soil samples.
- Sieved at < 2 mm.
- Weight 20 g of dry mineral soil and dispersed by shaking overnight in a 100 mL solution of sodium hexametaphosphate (5 g L^{-1}).
- Sieve the mixture through a 0.053-mm sieve and gently wash with deionised water (use 1 L of water approximately) the material retained above the sieve. The soil sample retained above the sieve is collected for POC determination, and the soil sample passing through the 0.053 mm sieve is collected for MOC determination.
- Weight the filters.
- Filter the soil sample (> 0.053 mm) for POC determination.
- Introduce the soil sample (< 0.053 mm) in the oven until the soil sample is dry for MOC determination. Weigh the dry soil.
- Introduce the filter + soil (> 0.053 mm) in the oven and dry at 60°C for 24 hours.
- Weight the filter + soil (> 0.053 mm) once dry.
- Remove the stones (in case you have) by hand.
- Weight the stones (in case you have).
- Grind the soil using a mortar and store it for carbon analysis. Concentrations of C in the isolated fractions will be determined using a C and N analyser.

Calculations

- POC fraction (g C kg⁻¹ soil) is calculated using the following expression:

$$\text{POC (g kg}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\frac{M_1 \times 100 \times C_1}{M_t}}{10}$$

- M₁ is the mass of soil > 0.053 mm (g)
- M_t is total mass of soil used at the beginning of the analysis (g)
- C₁ is the C concentration of the soil > 0.053 mm (%)

- MOC fraction (g kg⁻¹) is calculated using the following expression:

$$\text{MOC (g kg}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\frac{M_2 \times 100 \times C_2}{M_t}}{10}$$

WHERE

- M₂ is the mass of soil < 0.053 mm (g)
- M_t is total mass of soil used at the beginning of the analysis (g)
- C₂ is the C concentration of the soil < 0.053 mm (%)

Remarks

MOC fraction can also be determined by the expression $MOC = TOC - POC$, where TOC is total organic carbon, although this approach is less accurate.

The time in the oven will depend on the quantity of POC and MOC obtained (24 hours is the minimum).

As an alternative to removing the stones by hand, the dry soil could be sieved with a 1 mm sieve.

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06 GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS

6.1. Soil greenhouse gas emissions

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Principle & Application

Greenhouse gases (GHG) from soil such as CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ are key compounds that affect climate change. GHG fluxes are influenced by soil variables that influence microbial activity such as pH, NO₃⁻ or NH₄⁺, which, in turn, are controlled by a combination of soil properties (soil moisture, texture or structure) and soil management (IPCC 1995).

The method proposed in this protocol is based on the incubation of soil under a known temperature for 24 hours (Moreno-Barriga et al., 2017).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Precision balance
- Glass vials with crimp caps
- Syringe (5 mL)
- Vacutainer (5 mL)
- Gas chromatograph

REAGENTS

- Reference gases of known concentration

Procedure

- Weight 2 g of soil in a 25 mL glass vial closed with a crimp cap (incubation tube).
- Incubate the soil at 22° C during 24h.
- Take 5 mL of air with a syringe and transfer this volume into a vacutainer.
- Take the samples (vacutainer) to the laboratory and proceed with the analysis using gas chromatograph.

Calculations

N₂O, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions rates are calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{GHC concentration } (\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}) = \frac{\text{SM } (\mu\text{G}) \times \text{ITV (mL)} \times 1000}{\text{SV (mL)} \times \text{SW (g)}}$$

$$\text{SM } (\mu\text{g}) = \frac{\text{SC } (\mu\text{g L}^{-1}) \times \text{VV (mL)}}{1000}$$

$$\text{GHC concentration per hour } (\mu\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}) = \frac{\text{GHC concentration } (\mu\text{g kg}^{-1})}{\text{IT (h)}}$$

Where,

GHG concentration equation

GHG concentration = $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of the gas

SM = sample mass in vacutainer (μg)

ITV = incubation tube volume (mL)

1000 = unit conversion from g to kg

SV = volume of air taken in syringe (mL)

SW = soil sample weight (g)

SM equation

SC = sample concentration in vacutainer ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)

VV = vacutainer volume (mL)

1000 = unit conversion from L to mL

GHG concentration per hour equation

GHG concentration per hour = $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ of the gas

GHG concentration = $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of the gas

IT = incubation time (24h)

REFERENCES

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07 SATELLITE-BASED INDICATORS

7.1. Soil greenhouse gas emissions

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Principle & Application

Albedo is the amount of short-wave radiation reflected by a determined surface. Albedo is an important parameter to understand land surface energy and climate. It is measured in a scale from 0 (low) to 1 (high). Albedo has maximum values in the winter and minimum in the summer.

For instance, areas covered by snow or ice reflect approximately 80 % of the radiation back. Areas non-covered by snow or ice have a reduced albedo. However, there are differences between the different surfaces vegetation land cover has lower albedo than bare soils. Management have also impacted on albedo values. Soils affected by overgrazing increased albedo and drought (Liang and Wang, 2020).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the cloud mask from GEE repository for Landsat 8 Imagery (maskL8sr)
- Import Landsat 8 Surface Reflection Imagery 'LANDSAT/LC08/C02/T1_L2'
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Landsat 8:
 - startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the ROI (geometry)
- Apply the albedo formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMAP, QGIS)

Calculations

- Albedo is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Landsat 8 OLI imagery, based on Blue, Red, Near Infrared, Shortwave Infrared 1, and Shortwave Infrared 2 bands:

$$Albedo = \frac{((0.356*BLUE)+(0.130*RED)+(0.373*NIR)+(0.085*SWIR1)+(0.072*SWIR2)- 0.018)}{1.016}$$

where, BLUE corresponds to band 2, RED corresponds to band 4, NIR corresponds to band 5, SWIR1 corresponds to band 6 and SWIR2 corresponds to band 7. Figure 1 shows an example of Albedo assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. Albedo assessment example

REFERENCES

- Liang, S., Wang, J. (2020) Advanced Remote Sensing Terrestrial Information Extraction and Applications. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 956.

7.2. Land Surface Temperature

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Principle & Application

Land surface temperature (LST) is understood as the "radiative skin temperature of the land surface". LST dynamics depend mainly from the land use (e.g., vegetation, urban), albedo and soil moisture. This index is highly variable and responds to multiple factors such as cloud cover, aerosols or surface colors. LST is a key parameter for to assess water balance and surface energy.

In addition, affects the ecosystems and the organisms. LST is highly used in the assessment of urban climate, but also in the comparison between vegetated and non-vegetated areas. It is a good indicator of crops and vegetation conditions and greenhouse gases emissions (Liang, 2001).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- LST is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Landsat 8 OLI imagery, based on GEE code developed by Ermida et al. (2020).
- GEE code to generate a temporal composite LST image
- var LandsatLST =
require('users/sofiaermida/landsat_smw_lst:modules/Landsat_LST.js')
- var satellite = 'L8';
- var date_start = '2022-04-01';
- var date_end = '2022-09-30';
- var use_ndvi = true;
- var LandsatColl = LandsatLST.collection(satellite, date_start, date_end, geometry, use_ndvi)
- var lst = LandsatColl.median().clip(geometry);
- Export.image.toDrive({
- image: lst.select('LST'),
- description: 'LST_2022',
- folder: 'InBest',
- scale: 30,
- region: geometry,
- maxPixels: 10e11,
- crs: 'EPSG:4326'
- });

Calculations

- Please see Ermida et al. (2020). Figure 1 shows an example of LST assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. LST assessment example.

Remarks

- None

REFERENCES

- Ermida, S.L., Soares, P., Mantas, V., Göttsche, F.-M., Trigo, I.F. (2020). Google Earth Engine open-source code for Land Surface Temperature estimation from the Landsat series. *Remote Sens*, 12 (9), 1471. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12091471>.
- Liang, S. (2001) An Optimization Algorithm for Separating Land Surface Temperature and Emissivity from Multispectral Thermal Infrared Imagery. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 39, 264-274. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/36.905234>.

7.3. Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)

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Principle & Application

Gross Primary Productivity (GPP) is understood as the "total amount of carbon compounds produced by photosynthesis of plants in an ecosystem in a given period of time".

This index is normally used to estimate carbon sequestration, terrestrial energy, vegetation biogeochemistry and water cycle processes, and it is expressed in $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ hr}^{-1}$, $\text{tonnes C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import MODIS Terra Net Primary Production Gap-Filled Yearly Global 500m
- Define the filters to be applied:
- Startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-01-01 (example)
- Enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-12-30 (example)
- Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Select GPP variable
- Select first image
- Clip the composite to the ROI (geometry)
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcGIS, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- GEE code to generate an annual composite GPP image:
- `var dataset = ee.ImageCollection('MODIS/061/MOD17A3HGF')`
- `.filterDate('2022-01-01', '2022-12-30')`
- `.filterBounds(geometry)`
- `.select('Gpp');`

- `var gpp = dataset.first().clip(geometry);`

`Export.image.toDrive({`

- `image: gpp,`
- `description: 'GPP_2022',`
- `folder: 'InBest',`
- `scale: 500,`
- `region: geometry,`
- `maxPixels: 10e11,`
- `crs: 'EPSG:4326'`
- `});`

CALCULATIONS

GPP is calculated based on MODIS Terra Yearly Global Imagery, within GEE platform. GPP formula is the following:

$$\text{GPP} = \text{NPP} + \text{R}$$

Where NPP is the net primary production and R is the respiration

Figure 1 shows an example of GPP assessment in an agricultural field.

CALCULATIONS

Figure 1. GPP assessment example.

REMARKS

- None

7.4. Soil Sealing

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Principle & Application

Soil sealing is one of the most critical forms of degradation. Sealing is especially important in urban areas. When soil is sealed, it loses most of its functions and decreases the supply of essential ecosystem services.

Here, we assessed soil sealing following Elshehaby and Taha (2009), who defined the soil sealed in urban areas with the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) threshold equal to or lower than 0.02.

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
- Start date in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
- End date in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
- Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the Region of Interest
- Apply the NDVI formula
- Apply the threshold value
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)

GEE code to generate soil sealing based on a defined NDVI threshold value:

```
function maskS2clouds(image) {  
  var qa = image.select('QA60');  
  var cloudBitMask = 1 << 10;  
  var cirrusBitMask = 1 << 11;  
  var mask = qa.bitwiseAnd(cloudBitMask).eq(0)  
    .and(qa.bitwiseAnd(cirrusBitMask).eq(0));  
  return image.updateMask(mask).divide(10000);  
}
```


PROCEDURE

- var dataset =
ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED')
- .filterDate('2022-04-01', '2022-09-30')
- .filterBounds(geometry)
- .filter(ee.Filter.lt('CLOUDY_PIXEL_PERCENTAGE', 10))
- .map(maskS2clouds);

- var dataset = dataset.median().clip(geometry).select('B.*');

- var ndvi = dataset.normalizedDifference(['B8', 'B4']).rename("NDVI");

- var threshold = ndvi.gt(0.2); //ndvi values less than or equal to 0.2
- var soil = ndvi.updateMask(threshold)

- Export.image.toDrive({
 - image: soil,
 - description: 'Soil_Sealing_2022',
 - folder: 'InBest',
 - scale: 10,
 - region: geometry,
 - maxPixels: 10e11,
 - crs: 'EPSG:4326'});

CALCULATIONS

NDVI is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on the normalized difference between the Near Infrared (NIR) and Red bands:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{RED}}{\text{NIR} + \text{RED}}$$

where, Near Infrared (NIR) corresponds to band 8 and RED corresponds to band 4. After NDVI calculation, the areas with a threshold equal to or lower than 0.02 were masked. To validate spectral images, Google Earth Pro was used. For detailed validation, fieldwork is needed. An example of a soil sealing assessment is shown in Figure 1.

CALCULATIONS

Figure 1. Soil sealing assessment example.

REMARKS

- This index is targeted only for urban areas.

REFERENCES

- Elshehaby, A.R., Taha, L.G. Ed. (2009). A new expert system module for building detection in urban areas using spectral information and LIDAR data. Appl Geomat 1, 97-110

7.5. Drought stress index

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Principle & Application

The drought stress index (DSI) is based on the combination of two different indexes, Standardized Precipitation Index and heat index (Cho et al., 2020). It has been applied in several research fields such as agriculture or forestry.

The DSI assesses the capacity of the vegetation to resist to drought conditions. It is very useful to assess the crops capacity to support drought conditions. This index is highly variable throughout the year and is especially useful in cropland areas.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the ROI
- Apply the DSI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMAP, QGIS)

CALCULATIONS

DSI (Ponder III and McLeod, 1999) is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on Shortwave Infrared 1 (SWIR1) and Near Infrared (NIR):

$$\text{DSI} = \frac{\text{SWIR1}}{\text{NIR}}$$

where, SWIR1 corresponds to band 8 and NIR corresponds to band 11. Figure 1 show an example of DSI assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. Soil sealing assessment example.

REMARKS

DSI results are dependent on irrigation practices. This can mask the effects of droughts.

REFERENCES

- Cho, N., Kim, E., Lim, J.H., Seo, B., Kang, S. (2020). Developing drought stress index for monitoring Pinus densiflora diebacks in Korea. J Ecol Environ, 44, 15.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s41610-020-00156-9>.
- Ponder III, J.E., McLeod, K.W. (1999) Implications of relative drought stress index in Longleaf Pine from Thematic Mapper Data. Photogramm eng remote sensing, 65, 495-501

7.6. Moisture stress index

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Principle & Application

Water is a crucial element for plant growth. Moisture stress index is used to assess the vegetation moisture degree and applies in all environments. This is a good indicator of vegetation canopy health and yields in agricultural areas. MSI values range between 0 and 3. Green vegetation typically has MSI values from 0.4 to 31.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the ROI
- Apply the MSI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMAP, QGIS)

CALCULATIONS

MSI was calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on Shortwave Infrared 1 (SWIR) and Near Infrared (NIR):

$$\text{DSI} = \frac{\text{SWIR1}}{\text{NIR}}$$

where, SWIR1 corresponds to band 11 and NIR corresponds to band 8. Figure 1 show an example of MSI assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. MSI assessment example.

Figure 1. MSI assessment example.

REMARKS

MSI results are dependent on irrigation practices. This can mask the effects of droughts.

7.7. Normalized Difference Water Index

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Principle & Application

Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) was created to identify water areas (Feeters, 1996). Nevertheless, it is also useful to assess plant moisture and it is a very good proxy of water stress. It ranges from -1 (reduced moisture) to +1 (high moisture) and it is highly variable since depends on weather conditions (e.g., precipitation and temperature). Other aspects that can affect NDWI are land use changes and pests and diseases. This indicator is a good proxy to identify vegetation moisture content in forest and cropland areas.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the ROI
- Apply the NDWI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcGIS, QGIS)

CALCULATIONS

NDWI (Feeters, 1996) is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on the normalized difference between the Green and Near Infrared (NIR):

$$\text{NDWI} = \frac{\text{GREEN} - \text{NIR}}{\text{GREEN} + \text{NIR}}$$

where, GREEN corresponds to band 3 and NIR corresponds to band 8. Figure 1 shows an example of NDWI assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. NDWI assessment example.

REMARKS

None

REFERENCES

- Feeters, S.K. (1996). The use of the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) in the delineation of open water features. *Int J Remote Sens*, 17, 1425-1432

7.8. Normalized Difference Moisture Index

¹Miguel Inacio, ¹Manob Das, ¹Katažyna Bogdzevič, ¹Paulo Pereira

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Principle & Application

Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) is used to assess the vegetation water content. It is a good indicator to evaluate the water stress in different crops. It can detect at early stages vegetation water stresses and prevent negative impacts on yield. Also, it is an important indicator to assess fuel moisture in forest and cropland areas. Overall, this index is used to assess the water content in leaves.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the ROI
- Apply the NDMI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)

CALCULATIONS

NDMI (Wilson and Sader, 2002) is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on the normalized difference between the Near Infrared (NIR) and Shortwave Infrared (SWIR1):

$$\text{NDMI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{SWIR1}}{\text{NIR} + \text{SWIR1}}$$

where, NIR corresponds to band 8 and SWIR1 corresponds to band 11. Figure 1 shows an example of NDMI assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. NDMI assessment example.

REMARKS

None

REFERENCES

- Wilson, E.H., Sader, S.A. (2002) Detection of forest harvest type using multiple dates of Landsat TM imagery. *Remote Sens Environ*, 80, 385-396

7.9. Erosion Features

¹ Miguel Inacio, ¹ Manob Das, ¹ Katažyna Bogdzevič, ¹ Paulo Pereira

¹ Environmental Management Laboratory, Mykolas Romeris University, Vilnius, Lithuania.

Principle & Application

Erosion is a severe form of land degradation that impacts soil quality and the ecosystem services supplied. Identifying erosion features helps identify areas where the soil is subjected to a high intensification and the nutrient status is decreasing. Nowadays, different remote sensing products, i.e., Google Earth Online (<https://earth.google.com>) or Planet Images (<https://www.planet.com>; 3 m resolution), allow to identify at large and medium scales erosional features (Boardman, 2016).

This is an important advance for mapping and assessing erosional features.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV): If available.
- Appsheet (<https://about.appsheet.com/home/>).
- Computer with internet access to work with Google Earth online (<https://earth.google.com>);
- Planet images (<https://www.planet.com>)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- For small-scale plots (if available): Collect areal images from the area of interest using a UAV;
- For medium large-scale plots: Open Google Earth online and create a new project to identify different erosion evidence;
- Zoom in on the area of interest as close as possible to the land surface to identify areas where erosion features caused by water, wind or ice can be identified (e.g., rills, gullies, sheet erosion, splash erosion, fans, loess and sand deposits, till, cirques, horns).
- Vectorize the areas using polygon or line features according to the erosional feature identified. Some small-scale features may be difficult to identify and need to be assessed using images with a high resolution.
- Save all the polygons and line features. Open ArcMap or QGIS and convert KML to shapefile.

PROCEDURE

- Download images with a high resolution (Planet) and identify if the erosion features identified correspond to the ones identified in Google Earth online images. This is the first step of validation. Since planet images have a high resolution, it is important to see if more erosional features can be identified. The Google Earth online erosional features identification could be skipped, and the erosional features could be identified directly in Planet images. Nevertheless, starting with user-friendly software (e.g., Google Earth Online) is vital for inexperienced users. Once basic steps (e.g., vectorization, erosion features identification, and working with more advanced software, ArcGIS or QGIS) are mastered, It is advisable to work with planet images.
- Once the images are vectorized in the GIS environment, it is crucial to go to the field to validate the information identified. These two steps can be taken: 1) If available, use a UAV to identify the erosional features in situ. This is important to differentiate small erosional features (e.g., rill, sheet, splash erosion). 2) Use an application (e.g., Appsheet; it is needed to create an account) to identify if the erosional features identified in Google Earth Online and planet images correspond to reality.

An example of the procedure mentioned above is shown in figure 1.

CALCULATIONS

Figure 1. Erosional feature examples

REMARKS

The method must be applied carefully, and the analysis depends on the scale. Analysis conducted using Google Earth and Planet images can produce errors, and the erosion features can be assessed incorrectly. This is especially problematic if the area of interest is small and a more detailed analysis needs to be done (e.g., UAV fieldwork). For the results to be robust, it is important to do a field validation. It is essential to highlight that in agricultural areas, tractors can mask erosional features. Using remote sensing products to assess erosion features can be challenging in forested areas because canopy cover can mask them. Fieldwork is necessary to tackle this.

REFERENCES

- Boardman, J. (2016). The value of Google Earth™ for erosion mapping. *Catena*, 143, 123-127

7.10. Bare Soil Index

¹Miguel Inacio, ¹Manob Das, ¹Katažyna Bogdzevič, ¹Paulo Pereira

¹Environmental Management Laboratory, Mykolas Romeris University, Vilnius, Lithuania.

Principle & Application

The bare soil index (BSI) is a common indicator to assess the extent of bare soil or lack of vegetation. This index has been used to assess land degradation and soil erosion.

The index varies from -1.0 and $+1.0$. -1 represents the presence of vegetation, while $+1$ presence of bare soil. Values less than 0 normally occur in the non-growing season and values more than 0 are observed during the growing season. Surfaces occupied by glaciers, deserts, bare soil, snow cover or water have negative values.

On the other hand, vegetated areas during the growing season have positive values (Choubin et al., 2019). BSI has been used as a proxy for several indicators including, presence of vegetation, crop production, carbon stocks or erosion stabilization.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - Startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - Enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the Region of Interest
- Apply the BSI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)

- GEE code to generate a temporal composite BSI image:

- function maskS2clouds(image) {
- var qa = image.select('QA60');
- var cloudBitMask = 1 << 10;
- var cirrusBitMask = 1 << 11;
- var mask = qa.bitwiseAnd(cloudBitMask).eq(0)
- . .and(qa.bitwiseAnd(cirrusBitMask).eq(0));
- return image.updateMask(mask).divide(10000);
- }

- var dataset =
- ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED')
- .filterDate('2022-04-01', '2022-09-30')
- .filterBounds(geometry)
- .filter(ee.Filter.lt('CLOUDY_PIXEL_PERCENTAGE', 10))
- .map(maskS2clouds);

- var dataset = dataset.median().clip(geometry).select('B.*');

- var bsi = dataset.expression(
- '((SWIR2+Red)-(NIR+Blue))/((SWIR2+Red)+(NIR+Blue))',{
- 'SWIR2':dataset.select('B11'),
- 'Red':dataset.select('B4'),
- 'Blue':dataset.select('B2'),
- 'NIR':dataset.select('B8')
- }).rename("bsi")

- Export.image.toDrive({
- image: bsi,
- description: 'BSI_2022',
- folder: 'InBest',
- scale: 10,
- region: geometry,
- maxPixels: 10e11,
- crs: 'EPSG:4326'
- });

CALCULATIONS

BSI is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, base on the following formula developed by Diek et al. (2017):

$$BSI = \frac{((SWIR2 + Red) - (NIR + Blue))}{((SWIR2 + Red) + (NIR + Blue))}$$

where, Short Wave Infrared 2 (SWIR2) corresponds to band 11, Near Infrared (NIR) corresponds to band 8, RED corresponds to band 4 and Blue corresponds to band 2. Figure 1 shows an example of BSI assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. Erosional feature examples

REMARKS

The index is simple, easy to compute and assess. However, have several disadvantages such as data interpretation. For instance, is not possible to assess the differences between crops and vegetation types. Also, the results can be affected by weather conditions (e.g., rainfall, temperature).

REFERENCES

- Diek, S., Fornallaz, F., Schaepman, M.E., De Jong, R. (2017). Barest Pixel Composite for Agricultural Areas Using Landsat Time Series. *Remote Sens*, 9(12), 1245. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9121245>

7.11. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

¹Miguel Inacio, ¹Manob Das, ¹Katažyna Bogdzevič, ¹Paulo Pereira

¹Environmental Management Laboratory, Mykolas Romeris Univeristy, Vilnius, Lithuania.

Principle & Application

The normalized vegetation index (NDVI) is a common indicator of vegetation greenness used to assess vegetation health conditions. This index has been used to assess vegetation conditions in several land uses such as agriculture, grasslands, wetlands or forests.

The index varies from -1.0 and $+1.0$. -1 represents a healthy vegetation, while $+1$ shows the opposite. Values less than 0 normally occur in the non-growing season and values more than 0 are observed during the growing season. Surfaces occupied by glaciers, deserts, bare soil, snow cover or water have negative values.

On the other hand, vegetated areas during the growing season have positive values (Choubin et al., 2019). NDVI has been used as a proxy for several indicators including, vegetation growth and health, crop production, biomass, carbon stocks or erosion stabilization

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - Startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - Enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the Region of Interest
- Apply the NDVI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)

- GEE code to generate a temporal composite NDVI image:

- function maskS2clouds(image) {
- var qa = image.select('QA60');
- var cloudBitMask = 1 << 10;
- var cirrusBitMask = 1 << 11;
- var mask = qa.bitwiseAnd(cloudBitMask).eq(0)
- .and(qa.bitwiseAnd(cirrusBitMask).eq(0));
- return image.updateMask(mask).divide(10000);
- }

- var dataset =
- ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED')
- .filterDate('2022-04-01', '2022-09-30')
- .filterBounds(geometry)
- .filter(ee.Filter.lt('CLOUDY_PIXEL_PERCENTAGE', 10))
- .map(maskS2clouds);

- var dataset = dataset.median().clip(geometry).select('B.*');
-
- var ndvi = dataset.normalizedDifference(['B8', 'B4']).rename("NDVI");

- Export.image.toDrive({
- image: ndvi,
- description: 'NDVI_2022',
- folder: 'InBest',
- scale: 10,
- region: geometry,
- maxPixels: 10e11,
- crs: 'EPSG:4326'
- });

CALCULATIONS

NDVI is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on the normalized difference between the Near Infrared (NIR) and Red bands:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

where, Near Infrared (NIR) corresponds to band 8 and RED corresponds to band 4. Figure 1 shows an example of NDVI assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. NDVI assessment example.

REMARKS

The index is simple, easy to compute and assess. However, have several disadvantages such as data interpretation. For instance, is not possible to assess the differences between crops and vegetation types. Also, the results can be affected by weather conditions (e.g., rainfall, temperature).

REFERENCES

- Choubin, B., F. Soleimani, A. Pirnia, F. Sajedi-Hosseini, H. Alilou, O. Rahmati, A.M. Melesse, V.P. Singh, H. Shahabi. (2019). Effects of drought on vegetative cover changes: Investigating spatiotemporal patterns In: Assefa M. Melesse, Wossenu Abteu and Gabriel Senay (Eds.) Extreme Hydrology and Climate Variability Monitoring, Modelling, Adaptation and Mitigation, Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 213-222.

7.12. Net Primary Productivity

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¹ Environmental Management Laboratory, Mykolas Romeris University, Vilnius, Lithuania.

Principle & Application

The normalized vegetation index (NDVI) is a common indicator of vegetation greenness used to assess vegetation health conditions. This index has been used to assess vegetation conditions in several land uses such as agriculture, grasslands, wetlands or forests.

The index varies from -1.0 and $+1.0$. -1 represents a healthy vegetation, while $+1$ shows the opposite. Values less than 0 normally occur in the non-growing season and values more than 0 are observed during the growing season. Surfaces occupied by glaciers, deserts, bare soil, snow cover or water have negative values.

On the other hand, vegetated areas during the growing season have positive values (Choubin et al., 2019). NDVI has been used as a proxy for several indicators including, vegetation growth and health, crop production, biomass, carbon stocks or erosion stabilization

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import MODIS Terra Net Primary Production Gap-Filled Yearly Global 500m
- Define the filters to be applied:
- startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-01-01 (example)
- enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-12-30 (example)
- filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- select NPP variable
- Select first image
- Clip the composite to the Region of Interest (geometry)
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)

- GEE code to generate an annual composite NPP image:

- `var dataset = ee.ImageCollection('MODIS/o61/MOD17A3HGF')`
- `.filterDate('2022-01-01', '2022-12-30')`
- `.filterBounds(geometry)`
- `.select('Npp');`
- `var npp = dataset.first().clip(geometry);`
- `Export.image.toDrive({`
- `image: npp,`
- `description: 'NPP_2022',`
- `folder: 'InBest',`
- `scale: 500,`
- `region: geometry,`
- `maxPixels: 10e11,`
- `crs: 'EPSG:4326'`
- `});`

CALCULATIONS

NPP is calculated based on MODIS Terra Yearly Global Imagery, within GEE platform. Figure 1 shows an example of NPP assessment in an agricultural field.

Figure 1. NPP assessment example.

REMARKS

None

7.13. Plant senescing reflectance index (PSRI)

¹Miguel Inacio,¹Manob Das,¹Katažyna Bogdzevič,¹Paulo Pereira

¹Environmental Management Laboratory, Mykolas Romeris Univeristy, Vilnius, Lithuania.

Principle & Application

Plant senescing reflectance index (PSRI) measures the ratio between bulk carotenoids and chlorophyll. A high PSRI shows the onset of plant fruit ripening and canopy senescence.

This index has multiple applications such as crop production and yield, plant physiological stress detection and vegetation health monitoring.

This index is considered more advantageous than others such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (Anderegg et al., 2020).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - Startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - Enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
- Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the ROI
- Apply the PSRI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcGIS, QGIS)

- GEE code to generate a temporal composite PSRI image:

- function maskS2clouds(image) {
- var qa = image.select('QA60');
- var cloudBitMask = 1 << 10;
- var cirrusBitMask = 1 << 11;
- var mask = qa.bitwiseAnd(cloudBitMask).eq(0)
- .and(qa.bitwiseAnd(cirrusBitMask).eq(0));
- return image.updateMask(mask).divide(10000);
- }

- var dataset =
- ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED')
- .filterDate('2022-04-01', '2022-09-30')
- .filterBounds(geometry)
- .filter(ee.Filter.lt('CLOUDY_PIXEL_PERCENTAGE', 10))
- .map(maskS2clouds);
-
- var dataset = dataset.median().clip(geometry).select('B.*');

- var psir = dataset.expression(
• '(RED - BLUE) / (RED EDGE2)', {
• 'RED': dataset.select('B4'),
• 'BLUE': dataset.select('B2'),
• 'RED EDGE2': dataset.select('B6')
• }).rename("psir")

- Export.image.toDrive({
- image: psir,
- description: 'PSRI_2022',
- folder: 'InBest',
- scale: 10,
- region: geometry,
- maxPixels: 10e11,
- crs: 'EPSG:4326'

CALCULATIONS

PSRI (Merzlyak et al., 1999) is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based Red, Blue and Red Edge 2 bands:

$$PSRI = \frac{RED - BLUE}{RED\ EDGE2}$$

where, BLUE corresponds to band 2 and RED corresponds to band 4, and RED EDGE2 corresponding to band 6.

Figure 1. NPP assessment example.

REMARKS

None

REFERENCES

- Anderegg, J., Yu, K., Aasen, H., Walter, A., Liebisch, F., Hund, A. (2020) Spectral Vegetation Indices to Track Senescence Dynamics in Diverse Wheat Germplasm. *Front Plant Sci*, 10, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.01749>
- Merzlyak, M.N., Gitelson, A.A., Chivkunova, O.B., Rakitin, V.Y. (1999) Non-destructive optical detection of pigment changes during leaf senescence and fruit ripening. *Physiol Plant*, 106, 135-141.

7.14. Forest cover

¹Miguel Inacio,¹Manob Das,¹Katažyna Bogdzevič,¹Paulo Pereira

¹Environmental Management Laboratory, Mykolas Romeris University, Vilnius, Lithuania.

Principle & Application

Forest cover is essential to understand the quantity and quality of the ecosystem services supplied by a determined area.

Here we applied the NDVI threshold of >0.3 to identify the presence of the forest as described in Petorelli (2013).

EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
 - Startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
 - Enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
 - Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the Region of Interest
- Apply the NDVI formula
- Apply the threshold value
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)

- GEE code to generate forest cover based on a defined NDVI threshold value:

- ```
function maskS2clouds(image) {
```
- ```
  var qa = image.select('QA60');
```
- ```
 var cloudBitMask = 1 << 10;
```
- ```
  var cirrusBitMask = 1 << 11;
```
- ```
 var mask = qa.bitwiseAnd(cloudBitMask).eq(0)
```
- ```
    .and(qa.bitwiseAnd(cirrusBitMask).eq(0));
```
- ```
 return image.updateMask(mask).divide(10000);
```
- ```
}
```

- ```
var dataset =
```
- ```
  ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED')
```
- ```
 .filterDate('2022-04-01', '2022-09-30')
```
- ```
    .filterBounds(geometry)
```
- ```
 .filter(ee.Filter.lt('CLOUDY_PIXEL_PERCENTAGE', 10))
```
- ```
    .map(maskS2clouds);
```

- ```
var dataset = dataset.median().clip(geometry).select('B.*');
```
  
- ```
var ndvi = dataset.normalizedDifference(['B8', 'B4']).rename("NDVI");
```

- ```
var threshold = ndvi.gt(0.3); //ndvi values greater than 0.3
```
- ```
var forest = ndvi.updateMask(threshold)
```

- ```
Export.image.toDrive({
```
- ```
  image: forest,
```
- ```
 description: 'Forest_Cover_2022',
```
- ```
  folder: 'InBest',
```
- ```
 scale: 10,
```
- ```
  region: geometry,
```
- ```
 maxPixels: 10e11,
```
- ```
  crs: 'EPSG:4326'
```
- ```
}
```



# CALCULATIONS

NDVI is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on the normalized difference between the Near Infrared (NIR) and Red bands:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

where, Near Infrared (NIR) corresponds to band 8 and RED corresponds to band 4. After NDVI calculation, the areas with higher values than 0.3 were masked. Subsequently, the areas classified with forest cover were validated using Google Earth Pro. For a more detailed validation, field validation is necessary as well. Figure 1 shows an example of an area classified with forest cover.



Figure 1. NPP assessment example.

# REMARKS

The NDVI values for forest cover are different according to the other biomes. Therefore, it is crucial to find the threshold for the different biomes. In this case, we use it for temperate forests. However, this needs to be adjusted according to the area of interest biome.



## REFERENCES

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- Pettorelli, N. (2013). Normalized Difference Vegetation Index. Oxford University Press

## 7.15. Vegetation cover

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<sup>1</sup> Miguel Inacio,<sup>1</sup> Manob Das,<sup>1</sup> Katažyna Bogdzevič,<sup>1</sup> Paulo Pereira

<sup>1</sup> Environmental Management Laboratory, Mykolas Romeris University, Vilnius, Lithuania.

### Principle & Application

Vegetation cover is key for numerous ecological processes and ecosystem services supply such as air purification, flood and erosion regulation or pollination.

Here we assessed vegetation cover following EOS analytics guidelines that defined the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) threshold of  $>0$  as areas covered by vegetation.





# EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with Google Earth Engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

## PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2\_SR\_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
  - Start date in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
  - End date in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
  - Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the Region of Interest
- Apply the NDVI formula
- Apply the threshold value
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)



- GEE code to generate vegetation cover based on a defined NDVI threshold value:

- function maskS2clouds(image) {
- var qa = image.select('QA60');
- var cloudBitMask = 1 << 10;
- var cirrusBitMask = 1 << 11;
- var mask = qa.bitwiseAnd(cloudBitMask).eq(0)
- .and(qa.bitwiseAnd(cirrusBitMask).eq(0));
- return image.updateMask(mask).divide(10000);
- }
  
- var dataset =
- ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S2\_SR\_HARMONIZED')
- .filterDate('2022-04-01', '2022-09-30')
- .filterBounds(geometry)
- .filter(ee.Filter.lt('CLOUDY\_PIXEL\_PERCENTAGE', 10))
- .map(maskS2clouds);
  
- var dataset = dataset.median().clip(geometry).select('B.\*');
- 
- var ndvi = dataset.normalizedDifference(['B8', 'B4']).rename("NDVI");
  
- var threshold = ndvi.gt(0.15); //ndvi values greater than 0.15
- var vegetation = ndvi.updateMask(threshold)
  
- Export.image.toDrive({
- image: vegetation,
- description: 'Vegetation\_Cover\_2022',
- folder: 'InBest',
- scale: 10,
- region: geometry,
- maxPixels: 10e11,
- crs: 'EPSG:4326'
- });



# CALCULATIONS

NDVI is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on the normalized difference between the Near Infrared (NIR) and Red bands:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

where, Near Infrared (NIR) corresponds to band 8 and RED corresponds to band 4. After calculating the NDVI, the values higher than 0 were masked. Validation was conducted using Google Earth Pro. For more accurate validation, fieldwork is necessary. Figure 1 shows an example of areas covered by vegetation.



Figure 1. Vegetation cover assessment example.

## 7.16. Plant Phenology Index (PPI)

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### Principle & Application

Plant Phenology Index (PPI) characterizes the terrestrial vegetation canopy green leaf area dynamics and is close related to leaf area index. Phenology is understood as the biological cycles flowering and leaf unfolding. PPI can be relevant to predict plant canopy growth, important for vegetation monitoring.

This index is especially useful in coniferous forests, seasonally snow-covered areas (e.g., Northern latitudes) (Jin and Eklundh, 2014). Nevertheless, it has been used studies located in other areas (e.g., Africa, Tibetan Plateau, Iberian Peninsula).





# EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

## PROCEDURE

Plant phenology Index was calculated using the High-Resolution Phenology and Productivity dataset within Copernicus and Wekeo Services. PPI is assessed based on Sentinel 2 Imagery:

- Access PPI data on WEKEO database ([www.wekeo.eu](http://www.wekeo.eu)) – 'Seasonal Trajectories, 10-daily, LAEA projection'
- Define the Region of interest
- Define the temporal interval:
  - From (in the format MM-DD-YYYY): 01.04.2022 (example)
  - To (in the format MM-DD-YYYY): 01.04.2022 (example)
- Download PPI data (as raster file)
- Import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)
- Import the ROI as shapefile to GIS interface
- Clip the PPI raster using the region of interest



# CALCULATIONS

Figure 1 shows an example of PPI assessment in an agricultural field.



Figure 1. PPI assessment example

# REMARKS

This index is most suitable to boreal vegetation.

## REFERENCES

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- Jin, H., Eklundh, L. (2014). A physically based vegetation index for improved monitoring of plant phenology. *Remote Sens Environ*, 152, 512-525

## 7.17. Dry matter productivity

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### Principle & Application

Dry matter Productivity (DMP) measures the vegetation dry biomass formation for a determined month. This index is related to Net Primary Productivity. It is calculated in kilograms of gross dry matter per hectare per day.

DMP is very useful in assessing yield and monitoring crop conditions. Can detected anomalies in vegetation growth and is often used in agro-meteorological models to estimate yields.



# EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

## PROCEDURE

- DMP is extracted from <https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/dmp>
- Calculations
- DMP is calculated according to the following formula:
- $DMP = GDMP * 0.5$
- Where GDMP is the Gross Dry Matter Productivity.



Figure 1. DMP assessment example.

## 7.18. Leaf Area Index

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*Miguel Inacio, Manob Das, Katažyna Bogdzevič, Paulo Pereira*

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### Principle & Application

Leaf Area Index (LAI) describes the canopy structure and essential to understand the canopy structure. This index is also important to comprehend the mass and energy exchange between the biosphere and atmosphere. Leaf area Index is understood "as half the total area of green elements of the canopy per unit horizontal ground area".

LAI assess the total green area (canopy and understory vegetation). Overall, LAI quantifies the vegetation cover thickness. This index is one of the main drivers carbon balance, nutrient use, net primary production and water use.

LAI depends especially on climate, soil moisture, water and nutrients availability, carbon dioxide and light (Bréda, 2008).



# EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with google earth engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

## PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2\_SR\_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
  - startdate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
  - enddate in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
  - filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the Region of interest
- Apply the EVI formula
- Apply the LAI formula
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMAP, QGIS)



# CALCULATIONS

LAI (Boegh et al., 2022) is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI):

$$\text{LAI} = (3.618 \times \text{EVI}) - 0.118$$

$$\text{EVI} = 2.5 \times \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{RED}}{\text{NIR} + 6 \times \text{RED} - 7.5 \times \text{BLUE} + 1}$$

where, Near Infrared (NIR) corresponds to band 8 and RED corresponds to band 4, and BLUE corresponding to band 2. Figure 1 shows an example of Albedo assessment in an agricultural field.



Figure 1. PPI assessment example

## REFERENCES

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- Boegh, E., Soegaard, H., Broge, N., Hasager, C.B., Jensen, N.O., Schelde, K., Thomsen, A. (2002) Airborne multispectral data for quantifying leaf area index, nitrogen concentration, and photosynthetic efficiency in agriculture. *Remote Sens Environ*, 81, 179-193
- Breda, N.J.J. (2008). Leaf Area Index. In: Jørgensen, S.K., Fath, B.D. (Eds) *Encyclopedia of Ecology*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 2148-2154

## 7.19. Presence of Green Natural Elements

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<sup>1</sup>Miguel Inacio, <sup>1</sup>Manob Das, <sup>1</sup>Katažyna Bogdzevič, <sup>1</sup>Paulo Pereira

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### Principle & Application

The presence of green elements is an indicator of ecosystem vitality.

Here, we assessed the presence of green natural elements using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) of  $>0.2$ , following NASA Earth Observatory guidelines.



# EQUIPMENT & MATERIAL

- Computer with internet access to work with Google Earth Engine (GEE)
- GIS software (ArcMap, QGIS)

## PROCEDURE

- Import the (maskS2clouds) cloud mask from GEE repository for Sentinel 2 Imagery (maskS2clouds)
- Import Sentinel 2 Imagery ("COPERNICUS/S2\_SR\_HARMONIZED")
- Define the filters to be applied for the image collection of Sentinel 2 imagery:
  - Start date in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-04-01 (example)
  - End date in the format YYYY-MM-DD: 2022-09-30 (example)
  - Filter bounds using a defined geometry: in this case the ROI previously defined
- Apply the cloud mask to the image collection previously defined
- Create a median composite
- Clip the composite to the Region of Interest
- Apply the NDVI formula
- Apply the threshold value
- Export the image as raster file to Google Drive
- Download and import the raster file to GIS interface (ArcMap, QGIS)



- GEE code to generate the presence of natural green elements based on a defined NDVI threshold value:

- ```
function maskS2clouds(image) {
```
- ```
 var qa = image.select('QA60');
```
- ```
  var cloudBitMask = 1 << 10;
```
- ```
 var cirrusBitMask = 1 << 11;
```
- ```
  var mask = qa.bitwiseAnd(cloudBitMask).eq(0)
```
- ```
 .and(qa.bitwiseAnd(cirrusBitMask).eq(0));
```
- ```
  return image.updateMask(mask).divide(10000);
```
- ```
}
```
  
- ```
var dataset =
```
- ```
 ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED')
```
- ```
    .filterDate('2022-04-01', '2022-09-30')
```
- ```
 .filterBounds(geometry)
```
- ```
    .filter(ee.Filter.lt('CLOUDY_PIXEL_PERCENTAGE', 10))
```
- ```
 .map(maskS2clouds);
```
  
- ```
var dataset = dataset.median().clip(geometry).select('B.*');
```

- ```
var ndvi = dataset.normalizedDifference(['B8', 'B4']).rename("NDVI");
```
  
- ```
var threshold = ndvi.gt(0.2); //ndvi values greater than 0.2
```
- ```
var green = ndvi.updateMask(threshold)
```
  
- ```
Export.image.toDrive({
```
- ```
 image: green,
```
- ```
  description: 'Presence_Green_Elements_2022',
```
- ```
 folder: 'InBest',
```
- ```
  scale: 10,
```
- ```
 region: geometry,
```
- ```
  maxPixels: 10e11,
```
- ```
 crs: 'EPSG:4326'
```
- ```
});
```


CALCULATIONS

NDVI is calculated in Google Earth Engine platform, using Sentinel 2A MSI imagery, based on the normalized difference between the Near Infrared (NIR) and Red bands:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

where, Near Infrared (NIR) corresponds to band 8 and RED corresponds to band 4. After calculate the NDVI values, the values higher than 0.2 were masked. Validation of the results conducted were carried out using Google Earth Pro. For more detailed assessments, field validation is needed as well. Figure 1 shows an example of natural green areas assessment.

Figure 1. Green natural elements assessment example

REMARKS

The presence of green natural elements is highly dependent on the season, ecosystem assessment and management. For instance, in temperate environments or caducifolious forests, green elements are mainly visible during the Spring/Summer. In Mediterranean environments during the Summer, green elements are minimal. Also, irrigation affects this significantly (e.g., urban gardens). Therefore, adjusting the analysis time to the ecosystem assessed is important. Spring is the most appropriate to conduct in most cases.

08 CULTURAL INDICATORS

8.1. Cultural ecosystem services

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Common criteria for estimating indicators

Most cultural values are perceptual. To quantify it, it is necessary to link the land use and connect it with these perceptions.

The reference point for applying these indicators is the specific ecosystem service associated to the land use.

For example, in the restoration of a mine, the specific land use is associated to the mining area and can be located in a mountain range or elsewhere. In this mine there will be specific restored and unrestored ecosystems that correspond to the experimental treatments.

PRESENCE OF CULTURAL ELEMENTS

- Presence of physical/tangible elements (structures, objects) with a significant and social importance for cultural heritage (e.g., terraces, dry stone walls, watermills, churches...).
- Unit: 0/1 (discrete, binary)
- The indicator "presence of cultural elements" have the value of 1 if there are some (at least one) physical and tangible elements above ground with a significant and cultural heritage importance in the LL/LH. Otherwise is classified as 0.

PRESENCE OF ANCESTRAL VESTIGES

- Presence of ancestral vestiges (e.g., architectural structures, objects used by humans, paleosols, archaeological settlements, paleontological remains, etc.) with historical and remarkable importance for the site.
- Unit: 0/1 (discrete, binary)
- The indicator "presence of ancestral vestiges" has the value 1 if there are ancestral vestiges, such as architectural structures, objects used by humans, paleosols, archaeological settlements, paleontological remains architectural structures, objects used by humans, paleosols, archaeological settlements and/or paleontological remains below ground with significant and cultural importance in the LL/LH. Otherwise, is classified as 0.

PRESENCE OF TRADITIONAL ELEMENTS

- Presence of traditional elements linked to the ecosystem (e.g., traditional dishes, festivities).
- Unit: 0/1 (discrete, binary)
- The indicator “presence of traditional elements” has the value of 1 if there are some non-physical and intangible elements, such as festivities or traditional dishes, linked to the cultural and social customs and traditions in the LL/LH. Otherwise, is classified as 0.

PRESENCE OF ORIGIN CERTIFICATION LABELLING

- Presence of labels identifying the geographic indication of its origin, which is directly related to the assessed ecosystem (e.g., PDO, PGI).
- Unit: 0/1 (discrete, binary)
- The indicator “presence of origin certification labelling” takes the value 1 if there is at least one label of geographic indication of origin, such as PDO or PGI, for the products produced in the LL/LH. Otherwise, is classified as 0.

VISITORS AND ACCOMMODATIONS

Number of visitors to a site and number of tourist accommodations in the area.

Unit: (a) number of visitors/ha | (b) number of rooms/ha (continuous)

This indicator integrates two different but interrelated indicators:

- Number of visitors to the LL/LH (persons) with a recreational and leisure purpose. If such information is not specifically available for LL/LH, it could be extrapolated from the tourism local/regional statistics in case the LL/LH has a positive impact in the tourism in the region.
- Number of accommodations in the LL/LH (rooms) available for tourism, being either hotel, hostel, rural accommodations, camping, etc.

Recreation Index

Presence of infrastructure for recreation and accessibility to places

Unit: 0-1 Index (continuous)

The indicator "recreation index" is a composed index that seeks to measure the potential and the actual capability of the LL/LH to for recreation. So, it is based on their intrinsic characteristics (Paracchini et al., 2014), such their degree of naturalness and protection, presence of superficial water bodies, and the presence of cultural and geological heritage, and their capability to ensure such services, linked to the recreation infrastructure and accessibility to the LL/LH.

Remarks

The "recreation index" is based on the notion that recreation in the LL/LH depends on the presence of natural vegetation, biodiversity, presence of water bodies and proper accessibility and infrastructure.

Recreation Index

The factors above listed are an approximation of the influence they may have for the study area context. These factors are based on expert opinion and further factors may be added or removed when needed.

Therefore, the final discrete values of the Recreation Index may vary.

The "recreation index" (R) is therefore measured as:

$$R = PR + CR$$

Where PR represents the potential for recreation and CR summarises the capability for recreation, also defined as:

$$PR = N + P + A + G$$

- **Presence of natural vegetation (N)**

The "presence of natural vegetation" summarises a 0-1 discrete and binary index that has the value 1 if the LL/LH has natural vegetation (e.g., riparian vegetation, forest, emblematic natural plantations...) Otherwise is classified as 0.

Recreation Index

- **Presence of protected spaces (P)**

The “presence of protected spaces” summarises a 0-1 discrete and binary index has the value 1 if the LL/LH is in a protected area. Otherwise, is classified as 0.

- **Presence of water bodies (A)**

The “presence of water bodies” summarises a 0-1 discrete and binary index that has the value 1 if there are any superficial water bodies in the in the LL/LH Otherwise is classified as 0.

- **Presence of geological heritage (G)**

The “presence of geological heritage” summarises a 0-1 discrete and binary index that have the value 1 if the LL/LH exhibits important geological and geomorphological features with a high touristic and leisure value. Otherwise is classified as 0.

$$\mathbf{CR = MVA + LMV + I}$$

Recreation Index

- **Presence of accessibility infrastructures with limited use of motor vehicle (LMV)**

The “presence of accessibility infrastructures with limited use of motor vehicle” summarises a 0-1 discrete and binary index according to the presence of any infrastructures with limited use of motor vehicles (e.g., roads, paths and BTT/MTB routes, greenways, that provides access to the LL/LH. Otherwise, is classified as 0.

- **Presence of infrastructure for recreation (I)**

The “presence of infrastructure for recreation” is measured as a 0-1 discrete and binary index according to the presence of any infrastructure for developing recreation and leisure activities (e.g., recreational areas, ecological parks, bird observatories, interpretation centres, BTT centres, ski resorts...), Otherwise is classified as 0.

- **Presence of geological heritage (G)**

The “presence of geological heritage” summarises a 0-1 discrete and binary index that have the value 1 if the LL/LH exhibits important geological and geomorphological features with a high touristic and leisure value. Otherwise is classified as 0.

AESTHETIC LANDSCAPE INDEX

Perceived aesthetic value of photos.

Unit: 0-1 Index (continuous)

The indicator "aesthetic landscape index" is an index that seeks to measure, in an objective way, the aesthetic value of the landscape where the LL/LH are embedded. Through the aesthetic values (Likert scale 0-10) given by experts to representative photographs (Oteros-Rozas et al., 2018) of the LL/LH, it is possible to obtain an objective value of the aesthetic quality of the landscape of each study area.

EMPLOYMENT GENERATION

Annual work units (AWU) related to soil management.

Unit: AWU/ha/year (continuous)

The “employment generation” indicator will be measured through Annual Work Units (AWU) employed as labour in all the tasks needed for implementing and maintaining soil restoration actions in the LL/LH. An AUW corresponds to the minimum work done by a full-time employee. It is 1,800 hours (8 hours per day for 225 working days).

KNOWLEDGE GENERATION

Number of research projects, scientific papers, books, news, etc., related to the ecosystem.

Unit: Number of publications (continuous)

The “knowledge generation” indicator measures the number of scientific publications listed in some of the most widely used databases: Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com/>) and Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.es/>). It includes papers, books, conferences, and books chapters which develop the issues specifically located in the LL/LH during a certain period. It can also include news and TV documentaries and articles in newspapers.

Knowledge generation can be calculated as the sum of the total number of publications in the study area:

Knowledge generation = P + SJ + C + B + NW + TVD + TVN

Recreation Knowledge generation

Number of projects (National, Regional, European) (P)

The "number of projects" summarises a continuous variable about the total national, regional and/or European projects of the LL/LH.

Number of publications in scientific journals (SJ)

The "number of publications in scientific journals " summarises a continuous variable on the total number of articles published in national and international journals, with LL/LH as a case study.

Number presentations in conferences (oral/poster) (C)

The "number of presentations in conferences" summarises a continuous variable on the total number of oral presentations or posters presented at conferences, both national and international, with LL/LH as a case study.

Recreation

Knowledge generation

Number books/books chapters (B)

The "number of books books/chapters" summarises a continuous variable on the total number of books or book chapters in both national and international editorials, with LL/LH as a case study.

Number articles in newspapers (NW)

The "number of articles in newspapers" summarises a continuous variable on the total number of publications in local, national, and international newspapers, with LL/LH as a case study.

Number TV documentaries (TVD)

The "number of TV documentaries" summarises a continuous variable on the total number of documentaries on TV channels, both national and international, with LL/LH as a case study.

Number TV news (TVN)

The "number of TV news" summarises a continuous variable on the total number of news broadcasted on TV channels, both national and international, with LL/LH as a case study.

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InBestSoil

This project has received funding
from the European Union's Horizon
2020 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement
No 101091099

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